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ANNUAL REPORT
OF THE
ARCHÆOLOGICAL DEPARTMENT
GWALIOR STATE
FOR
Samvat 1985, Year 1928-29.

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ALIJAH DARBAR PRESS - LASHKAR.

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ANNUAL ADMINISTRATION REPORT
OF THE
DEPARTMENT OF ARCHÆOLOGY, GWALIOR STATE
FOR THE
Year ending 30th June 1929, Samvat 1985.

PART I.

I. Office Notes,

Charge.—The undersigned held charge of the Department throughout the year under report.

Members of the subordinate staff enjoyed leave as follows:—

1. *Photographer-Draughtsman.*—Sick leave for one month and ten days from 1st of July 1928 to 30th August 1929. Leave without pay for ten months and twenty days from 11th August 1928 to 30th June 1929.

2. *General Assistant.*—Privilege leave for two months and eleven days in different instalments.

3. *Assistant Photographer-Draughtsman.*—One month and seventeen days' privilege leave in different months.

4. *Officer Accounts.*—Nine days' privilege leave from 2nd November 1928 to 10th November 1928.

5. *Officer Correspondence.*—Ten days' privilege leave in the month of January 1929.

6. *Record-keeper.*—Thirty days' privilege leave in different parts of the year.

Appointments and Promotions.—The undersigned was allowed to draw the full budgetted pay of his post from 1st July 1928, under orders of the Council of Regency conveyed through the Home Member Sahib, Gwalior Government. Similarly the Home Member Sahib was pleased to grant promotion to the extent of the irrespective budgetted pay to the Inspector and General Assistant of this Department, from the auspicious occasion of His Highness' birthday.

Owing to the continued illness of the Photographer-Draughtsman the Assistant Photographer-Draughtsman discharged the former's duties in addition to his own, but gradually the work began to suffer and hence in the interest of work, the Assistant Photographer-Draughtsman was appointed from 23rd May 1928 temporarily to the Photographer-Draughtsman's post and Ganpat Singh, a local draughtsman, engaged on probation in place of the Assistant Photographer-Draughtsman, from the above date.

The Officer Accounts applied for retirement on gratuity on account of his failing health. The necessary procedure having been matured he was relieved from 17th May 1928 making over his charge to the Officer

Correspondence. But close of the financial year having approached, Mr. Mojumdar, a young undergraduate, was employed on probation to avert the work from falling into arrears.

General.—All the office staff discharged their respective duties, harmoniously, diligently and carefully for which I am glad to record my appreciation.

II. Administrative Changes and Orders.

No Circular or Departmental Order with special reference to this Department was issued in the year of report.

III. Work at Headquarters.

In addition to the ordinary routine of office, the following work was done during the headquarter season:—

1. An Annual Administration Report of the Archæological Department for the year Samvat 1984 was drawn up and submitted.
2. New acquisitions of antiquities in the Museum were classified, arranged and labelled.
3. A short history of the activities of the Department was prepared and submitted in compliance with the instructions of the Home Member Sahib with 15 photographs.
4. An album of important photographs taken during the year under report was prepared and submitted.
5. An illustrated guide to Chanderi was published.
6. A note on the Archæological Monuments in the State, not mentioned so far in Murray's Handbook, was drawn up and sent for inclusion in the revised edition of the book which was being brought out in the year of report.
7. A short brochure on 'Sight-Seeing at Gwalior' was drawn up for the delegates of the St. John's Ambulance Association held at Gwalior, at the request of the Medical Department.
8. Albums of select Archæological Monuments with short descriptive labels were prepared and presented to Their Excellencies and the party on the occasion of Their Excellencies' visit to Gwalior.
9. The coins received as treasure-trove finds or offered for sale and exchange by institutions and private individuals were examined and listed.
10. A note on a few Archæological Monuments in the State was sent to the India Society, London, for publication in the 'India Art and Letters'.
11. A note on the restoration of a colossal Jain rock-cut sculpture 'The Bavangaja' in Badwani State was drawn up and supplied at the request of the Restoration Committee.
12. An illustrated article on Abul Fazal and his tomb was contributed to 'Modern Review'.

13. Two Persian inscriptions from Chanderi were edited in the 'Epigraphia Indo-Moslemica.'
14. Short screen lectures on some of the Archæological Monuments were delivered (1) on the Anniversary day of the Vijaydharmasuri Memorial and the Jain institute at Shivpuri and (2) at three different Ganesa Mandals at Lashkar.
15. Annual Reports for V. S. 1981 and 1982 were carried through press.

IV. Tours.

During the year of report, the Superintendent spent 77 days in camp, partly for annual inspection of the monuments conserved already, for supervising and directing the works of conservation in progress, and partly for listing of monuments. The detailed tour diary will be found in Appendix A.

The Superintendent paid visits of annual inspection to the monuments at Surwaya, Antri, Bhilsa, Besnagar, Chanderi, Ujjain, Mandasaur, and Sondni. He supervised and directed the conservation works in progress at Gwalior, Udaygiri, Udaypur and Bagh and for listing the monuments at Gohad and Pipadi.

Moreover the Superintendent visited two places outside the State, namely, (1) Badwani, the capital of an Indian State of the same name in Central India, and (2) Rawerkhedi in the Khandwa District of the Central Provinces. The object and result of these visits are briefly described on pages 17 and 18 of this report.

The Archæological Inspector also made a month's tour for listing monuments.

V. Conservation.

During the year of report conservation of ancient monuments was carried out at Padhavli (District Tonwarghar), Lashkar (District Gird), Udaypur and Udaygiri (District Bhilsa) and Bagh (District Amjhera). The list of monuments conserved and the amount spent on the works is shown in Appendix B.

Padhavli (District Tonwarghar).—Remains of a large and ancient Hindu temple have been enclosed here in a later *gadhi* or fort. The temple which belonged probably to the latter half of 9th century A. C. has fine sculpture and carving in its surviving portions. With a view to free the temple from modern accretions and to make the fine sculpture and carving easily accessible for examination and study, this work was taken up in V. S. 1982 (*vide* that year's report) and some dismantling and excavation work was done. Along with preliminary clearance some repairs were also provided, but as the work of clearance progressed it was found necessary to expose a greater part of the plinth of the temple than originally intended and to repair the basement, before other items of the proposed repairs were carried out and consequently the work was suspended temporarily. This extra work required funds which could not be spared in

the succeeding year, owing to other urgent works. As new funds were not likely to come forth next year as well and as the grant for the postponed work was in danger of lapsing, the balance of postponed work was utilised in the year of report for carrying out a portion of the necessary excavation and dismantling.

Lashkar (District Gird).—As mentioned in the Archæological Report for Samvat 1984, the work of the restoration of the Chhatri of Maharani Lakshmibai of Jhansi sanctioned last year could not be started in that year as the proceedings for the acquisition of land round it were not completed. The land having been acquired, work was taken up and completed in the year of report. The following measures were executed :—

1. The existing Chhatri, having been totally shattered by the growth of Pipal and Nim trees, was dismantled and the trees rooted out.
2. The original Chhatri consisted of a small square kiosque placed on a platform. The upper portion of the kiosque had totally disappeared by the growth of trees, leaving the lower platform and basement of kiosque. Besides there were no steps to the Chhatri or kiosque. The platform was rebuilt from the very founds using the old carved stone as much as available and a flight of steps added.
3. The basement of old Chhatri was also built with slight alteration omitting kiosque, as nothing had survived to give an idea of its form.
4. A cut-stone receptacle carved approximately in the style of 10th century for the holy plant of *Tu'si* as an appropriate object, was set up as is customary with such monuments.
5. The upper platform was further made to carry four inscriptions one on each face. Of these those facing east and north have compositions in Marathi and Sanskrit verse, respectively. The remaining two are in Hindi and English giving a short note of the incident with dates of birth and death of Maharani of Jhansi and the year of conservation.
6. The Chhatri stood on a neglected piece of land having a prominent position along the main road from city to station. Hence this land was acquired and tidied up to enhance the beauty of the monument, by
 - (a) building a low compound wall,
 - (b) providing an iron railing on it,
 - (c) levelling the ground inside,
 - (d) setting up stone benches,
 and (e) adding a decent entrance with steps, as the ground level is about three feet above the road.

It is proposed to provide a small garden round the Chhatri next year.

Later on it was found that the short inscriptions put up were not considered sufficient by the visitors hence another inscription in English and Hindi giving a brief history of the Maharani's life and activities was set up close to the Chhatri in the same compound

Narwar (District Narwar).—The only work done here consists of putting up some name-boards for the guidance of visitors to (1) a mosque near Hawa Paur, (2) two boards pointing to Kachcheri mahal, (3) one board pointing a footpath to Kachcheri mahal through the ruined palaces and another two pointing to Catholic church and cemetery.

Udaypur (District Bhilsa).—The town possesses a fine temple of 11th century known as Udayesvar or Nilkanthesvar. It has been described at length in the Annual Report of V. S. 1980 in which year this monument was first taken up for conservation. As the funds were available in small amounts work was done in instalments and is mentioned in the preceding Archaeological Reports. The only work left to be done was that of the compound wall and removal of a portion of debris left at remote ends of the extensive corners of the compound and the heavy debris unearthed in dismantling. The following items were therefore carried out in the year of report:—

- (a) The heaps of debris were dug up and removed beyond the premises.
- (b) All the heavy debris carved or otherwise were removed from the compound with the exception of a few which were exhibited along the compound wall as pieces of art.
- (c) The main entrance to the yard of the temple on the east was fully exposed up to the present street level by digging up the debris in which it was buried. This operation exposed also the two dwarfpalas flanking the staircase.
- (d) The remains of attendant shrines were cleared and their living members set right.
- (e) On fully dismantling the unsightly compound wall the plinth of the original compound was traced all round. The exposing or restoring the originally carved wall fully, would require enormous amount of money which was neither permissible nor necessary. The compound wall above the plinth only has been brought round in the following way, leaving the unexposed plinth as it is.

On the east near the main entrance, it was restored on both faces after its original form by old pieces of stones from other parts of the compound.

A portion was built up by means of old carved pieces and rounded up by course of placing coping.

The remaining portion was completed by plain masonry with a fourth coping, keeping a height of the original wall.

The main entrance on east is a wide one and gives entry to cattle. As a gate would involve obstacle a zigzag entrance was made by building

small walls, to allow people only a free entrance. Similarly on west the main entrance has already been provided with an iron gate. The pujaries were ordered to keep the gate closed in their absence from temple. But to allow people to come in, a zigzag entrance has been made near it also.

Most of the sunken and crushed floor of the yard has been reset as was found necessary.

The crevices in the floor inside the main temple were made good by cement concrete.

Two *samais* or brass lamps with post were set up in the shrine room.

The whole temple was washed inside to diminish the bad sight produced by modern white-wash.

Short description printed in Hindi and English in glass frames were put both in the temple as well as the mosque on the back of the temple.

Minor Monuments at Udaypur.

Besides the above, some partial conservation work was done at the following:—

- (1) *Mosque of the time of Sultan of Mandu.*—
 - (a) Jungle clearance and removing cactus bush enveloping the monument.
 - (b) Clearing of debris inside.
 - (c) Resetting the floor.
 - (d) Dismantling a portion of unsightly modern wall and platform.
- (2) *Bara Khambi.*—
 - (a) Clearance of jungle and cactus bush.
 - (b) Resting a leaning pillar plumb right.
 - (c) Renewing gaps of cut-stone masonry.
 - (d) Removing debris
- (3) *Kanugo's Sati.*—
 - (a) Jungle clearance and tidying up.
- (4) *Pisnari's temple.*—
 - (a) Clearing jungle.
 - (b) Removing cactus bush.
- (5) *Mughal palace.*—
 - (a) Jungle clearance.

Udaygiri (District Bhilsa).—In the Udaygiri hill there is a group of 20 rock-cut Hindu and Jaina caves ranging in date from 5th to 9th century A. C. Being situated in the vicinity of Sanchi, as well as having been advertised, these caves and other monuments at Bhilsa are visited now by thousands of visitors.

These caves have been conserved and cleared partially in previous years. The following works were done here in the year of report :—

- (a) Some of the caves were infested with bats and were often entered by cattle; to check it shutters with expanded metal netting have been provided.
- (b) In a few caves some stone had been decayed and crumbled off and entailed danger to them. These decaying portions were further chiselled to firm surface and whole restored with cut-stone masonry to match.
- (c) The caves being situated at the sloping foot of the hill, the ground in front of the caves is generally uneven and subject to rain cuts. This ground was levelled in steps by providing short retaining walls and dressing the surface to easier grade.
- (d) A few of the caves are situated on or near the top of the hill, and to visit them was difficult at times without a guide. A regular footpath has been made connecting all the caves. The ups and downs have either been sloped or converted into steps, by chiselling rock or building with masonry.
- (e) Besides the caves on the top of the hill, there was formerly a big temple with monolithic pillar whose basement is only exposed after recent excavations in previous years. This site was cleared off jungle and tidied up as a monument.
- (f) Two stone notice boards were set up to warn the people against vandalism and damage to monuments.
- (g) Two stone signboards were set up along the Bhilsa-Shamshabad Road at the junction of tracks to Udaygiri and Khambaba.
- (h) A fair-weather road was made in the past at the foot of the hill for convenience of visitors. It was proposed to be metalled but as a scheme of metalled road is under consideration, the proposal of metalling the existing road was given up. The existing road was however improved by widening to 12 feet, providing with drains and earthwork and spread over with a thick coat of river sand.

Bagh (District Amjhera).—The special grant allotted for the partial conservation of the Bagh caves in V. S. 1983, was all spent up last year except a portion of it which was meant for the arrangement for protecting the fresco paintings on cave No. 4. The final decision took much time and was arrived at only about the end of the last year when little time was left to take up the work. This work was executed this year and consisted of a wooden-frame fixed in the frescoed rock-wall clear of the paintings. A number of shutters of convenient size on slip-in devise was provided so that all the shutters can be removed at any time without obstructing the painted surface to the eye.

Further special grant was also requisitioned in the previous years but no sanction was received in the year of report.

However, the clearance of most of the debris from inside the cave No. 4, exposed a greater part of the fragile and crumbling rock-surface which was not hitherto exposed to the direct effect of the climate. Thus the exposed portions began to threaten in more than one ways. Some of the cracks began to widen slowly, while here and there portion of overhanging rock, particularly over the central door gave way. In order to check this, emergent work which (consists of rail iron frames in the doors and window openings of the cave No. 4) was executed in advance and paid from the ordinary budget of the Department.

Miscellaneous.

A name-panel showing the way to the tomb of Abul Fazal at Antri was set up along the Gwalior-Jhansi Road near Makora Dak Bungalow to attract visitors to this monument.

Lands were acquired connected with the monuments at Bagh, Suhania and Pawaya for preserving the loose antiquities, tidying up and for neat maintenance of the surroundings at these places.

VI. Annual Upkeep.

Annual clearance and petty repairs were carried out to all important groups of monuments already conserved. Besides, new permanent caretakers were appointed to look after the important monuments at Bhilsa and the Chhatri of Maharani Lakshmibai of Jhansi in the year of report.

It is a practice with the Department to put descriptive notices about the monuments either along with the conservation or later as soon as practicable. Such notices were set up at Udaypur, the Gujari Mahal, Chhatri of Maharani Lakshmibai of Jhansi at Gwalior and other monuments at Badoh.

VII. Exploration.

(a) Excavations.

No excavations could be taken up this year, as other monuments above ground and whose conservation was incomplete, required more attention.

(b) Listing of Monuments.

Sixty-one monuments situated in 18 different places, in the districts of Esagarh, Narwar, Bhilsa and Bhind, were listed during the year of report. Appendix C shows a list of monuments newly listed. They may be described briefly as under:—

(District Bhilsa.)

Udaypur.— This old and deserted town possesses some fine monuments of the mediæval period, of which the Udayesvar temple is the most charming and prominent (*vide* Annual Report for V. S. 1980, page 5). This village lying beside the old road from Delhi to Deccan, did not escape the notice of the Muhammadan rulers and consequently it contains numerous ruins of mosques and tombs. Some of these of more importance have already been listed and the following were noticed during the year of report.

Outside Motia Gate of the town and within 200 feet of it, stands a small 15th century mosque made of fine dressed stone masonry. It has not much carving, but is plain and massive; the usual characteristic of the Mandu style, since it was built in the reign of Sultans of Mandu. It has only a prayer hall with a small chabutra in front. Later on this chabutra has been extended by putting a rubble wall and utilised as a graveyard. All this later work gave room to intense vegetation and made the original monument obscure so far. It has two inscriptions, one of which over the central niche in the prayer hall is in Persian and records the construction of mosque in A. H. 894 (see No. 27 in Appendix D). The other inscription is on a block of stone built up in the left wall flanking the chabutra, and is contemporary with the Persian inscription.

Another small mosque built up in almost the same style as the foregoing one, stands in the western corner of the town inside *Chatur* Gate. The only difference is that it has a wider platform for the graves, which is contemporary to the mosque. Some of the grave stones are inscribed over with verses of Koran. An inscription over the central niche places its construction in A. H. 954 (*vide* inscription No. 31, Appendix D) during the reign of Islam Shah Suri of Delhi.

Besides there were noticed three more mosques which bear inscriptions of the Moghul Emperors but are of little interest from architectural point of view (*vide* inscription Nos. 28 to 30, Appendix D).

District Bhind.

Gohad.—This place has also been visited and the monuments listed. This year it was visited to examine certain tombs said to belong to some distinguished persons but what could be found was as under :—

To the south west of the Gohad Dak Bungalow in a field stands a tomb, consisting of an oblong platform about 3 ft. high with tall wall at its head some 20 feet, in height. This wall has a decoration partially consisting of two pillars of daric style supporting an entablature which carries a semi-carved end of the wall decorated with cornice. Midway between the top of the platform and end of the head-wall is set up a tablet which mentions one Pierre Lambert (*vide* inscription No. 33, Appendix D) who died in 1780 A. D.; but who he was is uncertain. According to available history, he might be one of the French gunners in the service of the Rana of Gohad. There is another smaller tomb close to it, but it has got no reference.

Close to the above tomb is a field, said formerly to be a garden and has well, built up with fine dressed blocks of stone. It bears one Persian and two Hindi inscriptions. From one of these, it appears to have been built in the reign of Rana of Gohad, in A. D. 1782.

Within the limits of a hamlet Banipura in the suburb of Gohad there stand two tombs in a field, consisting of raised oblong platforms and tops finished with carved conical spires. The whole is finished in plaster, with plain mouldings. Nothing is known of its inmates.

Gohadi.—Is a small village a mile to the south of Gohad town on the other bank of the river Vesli. The village has some ruins of 10th century temple and a memorial stone lying prostrate. Half a mile further south of the village stands a square column built of rubble stone faced with ashlar facing and is topped over with a cone. It is also said to be a tomb but to whom it is sacred is not known.

Pipadi.—This village is a mile and a half to the north-west of Gohad Road Station. It has traces of 10th century temples and their stray pieces heaped in groups. Besides, there stand two sculptures in field back to back; one representing a Nagi and other is a male figure. A crude memorial stone also stands in the village.

District Esagarh.

Mungaoli.—Is a fairly good town. Formerly it was the headquarter of Subat but now it has a Tehsil, a Judicial Office, Police Station, Post Office and Jail and also a Railway Station. A metalled road from this place runs to the historical place of Chanderi. The place was examined only through curiosity this time and the following monuments were noticed :—

Malkhana Boadi.—This is a step-well, built of fine dressed blocks and has close resemblance to those of Chanderi step-wells of its period. It bears a broken inscription in a niche flanking the main passage and refers to its construction during the reign of Ghias Shah Sultan of Mandu in A. H. 900? = A. D. 1494. This step-well is situated on the back of the present Tehsil Office in a garden.

Jama Masjid.—This is situated at the southern end of the market in the town. It bears no inscription and the only significance of the mosque is that many pillars of the mediæval temples have been built in the prayer hall erected on pillar and lintel style. It is quite simple on plane as well as in architecture.

District Narwar.

Bara.—also known as Bhoj-ka-Bara, is a village about six miles to the north-west of Satanwada and is at present situated in a plain at the foot of the hill but formerly occupied the top and slopes of the very hill as evinced by the ruins. The present village is quite destitute of any monument ancient or modern, except some fragments of old carvings lying here and there probably hurled from the top of the hill, which must have had some 10th century temples.

The hill above possesses ruins of modern gadhi which was probably built up in the 16-17th century by some ambitious Muhammadan headman, nothing of whom has now survived. The ascents to the hill are two, one through the ruins of the village which is flanked by gateways up to the top end and the other one faces the present village and is a sort of trodden path with crude steps here and there. Along this passage about halfway, is a detached piece of rock with the ruins of a single modern dwelling and is said to be the seat of one Bhoja who was a shepherd and possessed a charming flute. He would sit here attracting all animals of the jungle

round him and even control his flock with the miracle of his flute. It is after this Bhoja that the village is still called Bhoj-ka-Bara to differentiate with other Baras.

Some of the noteworthy ruins are detailed in Appendix C, and need no more particular description.

Karari Ahmadpur.—This is a mere hamlet and lies on the foot of another hill a mile and a half to the east of Bara and is met first when coming from Satanwada and lies on the same track. This village also once stood halfway on the hill.

The only monument met with here is a small shrine of Siva of the 12th century. The *shikara* and the outer casing and the sanctum are gone and only a carved door frame $2' \times 3' 11''$ and a porch $5' \times 6'$ are all what is left now. No sculpture was seen close to it. The temple stands on a mound which forms part of the *bund* of a small tank.

A loose Sati-stone with a badly damaged inscription was also lying along a modern *Tibara* in the cremation ground and is of no particular interest.

Dongar.—About four and half miles to the south-east of Satanwada lies this petty good village midway between Narwar and Shivpuri along the Moghul road to Deccan. It was reported to contain some monuments but the examination revealed no good result. Among those worthy of mention are detailed in Appendix C (but for the inscription on them, there is no feature work description). One dried up step-well with inscription, a tomb with inscribed grave stone and a small mosque all work of one man who was perhaps a petty officer in this town are situated in this village on the back of the Zamindar's house and are said to be in the midst of a garden.

To the north-east of the village about $1\frac{1}{4}$ miles away is another step-well, called Shahi Baodi, on the old highway to Deccan. The inscription which is in Hindi refers to its construction in V. S. 1738=1671 A. D. Apart from its historical importance, its value as a source of water is great, as it stands in the verge of hill ridge where water could not be had two miles all round. At the time of visit it was found all silted up and almost dry, but is worthy to be reclaimed.

Tongra.—This is a village some eight miles to the south-west of Shivpuri and the present population is on a laterite hillock overlooking a tank at its foot to the north. The cart track from Shivpuri passes through its former site and after running over the dam of the tank ascends the village. Naturally the new site has nothing of archæological interest. The old site which is now a mere *kheda* is being utilised for cultivation but the ruins still possess some noticeable objects of antiquary.

The most important antiquity recovered from the site is a sculpture of Nrisimha, incarnation of Vishnu, killing the demon Hiranya Kashyap and an inscription is engraved on its back (*vide* Appendix D, No. 59). This sculpture has been removed to the Archæological Museum at Gwalior,

There is a particular type of temples met with here. In these temples the shrine-room is generally oblong and narrow, has a low flat roof and its walls both inside and outside are built of plain and dressed blocks. The *sabhamandapa* or porch is decorated with carving, both out and inside, as well as the door frame of the sanctum, opening into the porch. The porch is generally provided with raised seats with back rests. The general character of architecture and carving is akin to that of 10th and 11th century A. D.

Six temples of the above type in a more or less ruined state are seen here. All have been deprived of their deities and from the dedicatory blocks of the shrine doors, two of them were dedicated to Surya and the rest to Vishnu. Among loose sculptures near these temples that of Kamal, Surya, Ganesa and a big sculpture of Hanuman may be mentioned.

Another monument worth noticing is a small square pillared hall ($8\frac{1}{4} \times 8\frac{1}{4}$) situated in close vicinity of the above temples. It resembles in style of carving to that of the temples and has similar seats, with back rests on three sides. The outer plinth is complete in the round and hence it cannot be the porch of the temple. Neither any other ruin exists close to it to which it was adjacent nor its exact purpose can be said.

Besides, there are few Sati-stones belonging to this village. Two of them stand about three furlongs to the east of the village and two about the same distance on the west. All are uninscribed and roughly belong to the 15th or 16th century A. D.

To the north of the village on the north bank of the tank is a modern tomb of a *pir* where a mela is held annually in the dark half of the *vaishakh*. The martyr is said to be one Ali Khan, a pushing soldier from Ajmere, who intended to alarm the Raja of Narwar. The Raja of Narwar taking heed of him sent his general Khanderao who checked and defeated him at the spot and carried his head to his master leaving his trunk which was interred by Ali Khan's followers in this tomb. Although nothing can be said about Ali Khan, yet Khanderao is a known personage of the 17th century A. D. and connected with Narwar. The people in the vicinity revere the tomb and believe in the blessings of the *pir*.

Shivpuri.—This is a well-known place, being the summer capital of Maharaja Scindia. It is situated 74 miles, south of Gwalior, on the Agra Bombay trunk road. The population is divided into two distinct divisions. The portion of this town lying west of the road is mostly modern settlement, being formerly a British cantonment is called Chhavani, while the eastern portion is known as *purani* (old) Shivpuri. This old town possesses some monuments which have already been listed. The new one noticed this year is a grave stone carved in the form of a bedstead and showing the plaids of cotton tape used in stringing. It is in a fair state of preservation and is placed over a raised platform to the south-east corner of Hira Sha's grave yard flanking the road.

The following places though lying within the jurisdiction of Narwar District are virtually villages in the Jagir of Sardar Bade Shitole Sahib.

All these villages are situated along the pucca road connecting Pohri, the headquarter of the Jagir with Mohna, a Railway Station on the Shivpuri Section of the Gwalior Light Railway at a distance of 40 miles.

Bhatnawar.—This is a big village about 5 miles to the north of Fohri. A few years back a damaged inscription of 7th to 8th century was picked up by Babu Jugal Kishore, District Engineer, which created an attraction for the examination of the spot. Curiously enough, nobody in the village could point out the place from which it was picked up nor any remains contemporary with the inscriptions were seen.

The only remains noticed is a dilapidated 10th century temple—almost extinct to the south=west of the village flanking the road. Only a few carved debris and sculptures are seen in a modern flat-roofed room close to the ruins and are worshipped as Mata quite erroneously. The sculptures are clearly of Brahma, Vishnu, Shiva and Parvati but are all now bismear-ed with the usual red lead and clad in female dress. Close to this Mata temple is another broken room in which the pieces of sculptures are heaped up but are of no particular importance. A crude Sati-stone also stands close to it and is uninscribed.

Berad.—This is a petty good village 10 miles beyond Bhatnawar. This village was to be of much antiquity. The tradition current is that the present name is a perversion of *Virat-Nagar*—the old historic place where the Pandavas spent a part of their exile. Close to this village is another village to be described below in which stands the house of *lac* (sealing wax) built for burning alive the Pandavas.

Nothing however of any antiquarian interest was met with here. All that could be seen was crude Sati-stones, a few carved debris of 10th century temples lying sparingly and a few broken sculptures without any trace of actual monuments. What is traceable is a site of a single small temple facing east and is buried in a Zamindar's open cattle shed. Only a portion of shrine wall has survived with which are resting three sculptures. Two of these are broken. The one in the centre is a standing Jain Tirthamkara.

Kalamadh.—Is a small village half a mile to the south of Berad and is populated on craggy soil. The village is said to be a part of Berad village, though the later decay has now separated them. In the heart of the village stands a ruined temple similar in plane and style to those of Tongra described in the preceding paras. Both shrine room and *sabhamandapa* are oblong measuring $9\frac{1}{2} \times 6\frac{3}{4}$ feet, and 48 ft. $\times$ 14 $\frac{1}{2}$ ft. respectively. The roof of both of these has fallen off. The enclosing walls are built of plain dressed blocks of stones and no decoration of carving is seen. Outside the *sabhamandapa* was another room probably of the same size, as the extension of a cross wall of *sabhamandapa* room warrants. The ground round the temple is raised up and the original plinth is therefore not open to view.

In the shrine-room lies a broken sculpture of Man Varaha, 3 ft. wide and 6 ft. high, which shows that the temple was sacred to Vishnu. An-

other loose Jain sculpture is placed in the shrine-room but it seems to have been imported from somewhere else.

The temple walls are quite weather-worn and almost blackened by the effect of rains. Traditionally the temple is known as Kalamadh (black temple), from which the village takes its name. According to another tradition this very temple is the house modelled from *lac* (sealing wax) which was built by Kichak. Pandavas on their retreat are said to have taken shelter in this house, which was set on fire according to a pre-conceived intrigue. It has since been ruined and blackened by fire and came to be known as Kala-madh. The villagers still attribute a ruined temple door as the outer openings of the under ground passage which carried the Pandavas out of this house of fire. This ruined temple lies some three furlongs north of Kala-madh at the foot of the dam of the tank. The temple which was probably sacred to Siva is almost buried in ground and shattered and reduced to heaps. On a modern platform close by is a modern image of Hanuman and near it is placed a linga with Jaladhari which probably belongs to this ruined temple.

Bhadra.—Half a mile to the east of Berad on the other side of the road is another small village. It possesses no antiquities, but abounds in Sati-stones some of which are inscribed.

Girvani.—This is a small hamlet just on the road nearly midway between Mohna and Pohri. The only monument noticed is a ruined temple flanking the road and facing the east. What have survived of the temple are the two plain walls of the shrine-room running at right angles and represent the northern and southern end and support to a few fine sculptures. The temple was probably sacred to Goddess Kali as a sculpture of the goddess though broken is the biggest in the group. This temple was also probably in the Tongra style as the traces of the shrine-room measure $14' \times 10'$. Among other sculptures, those of Indrani ($2' \times 5\frac{1}{2}'$) and Kaumari ($2' \times 5\frac{1}{4}'$) are worth removing to Museum being in the preserved condition so far. Other pieces represent Parvati, Varahi and other minor goddesses.

Semar Khedi.—This is a small village lying on the Mohna-Pohri road in the 16th mile, but is away about a mile from it. The village itself could not be examined for want of time. But at the limits of this village is a modern tank called Sarwan Tal which flanks the road. Below the bound of this tank within 50 feet of the road lie the ruins of two Siva temples facing north. The temples are almost extinct, but what is worth noticing is a sculpture probably belonging to one of these temples now placed or rather stuck up on a modern platform close to it in line. It is $1\frac{3}{4}$ ft. wide by 2 ft. high and represents a forty armed goddess whose head and torso are gone. The feet and hands with different objects in hands are seen. Ruins belong roughly to 12th century A. D.

VIII. Epigraphy.

Sixty inscriptions have been noticed or copied in the year under report ranging in date from the 5th to 19th century A. D.

Twenty-seven of these are in Hindi, fourteen in Persian, thirteen in Sanskrit, five in Arabic and one in English.

The earliest and by far the most important of them is a copper-plate inscription found in the debris of Bagh cave No. 2. It is inscribed in Gupta characters of the 5th-6th cent. A. D. and is in Sanskrit. Although the letters recording the date are obliterated there is no difficulty in assigning it to the 5th or 6th century on paleographical grounds. It records the grant of a village by king Subhandhu of Mahishmati, which has been identified with the modern Omkar-Mandhata on the river Narbada, the popular place of pilgrimage and famous for the temple of Omkaresvara, to Buddhist monks for their maintenance, upkeep of the monastery and worship of Lord Buddha. This inscription invariably removed all doubt as to the period of the construction of the Bagh caves and their antiquities.

Next to this comes an inscription, dated in Vikrama Samvat 1082 = 1025 A. D. from Tongra (District Narwar), which is written in Sanskrit and records the construction of a temple of Hari (Vishnu).

Six of them are Sati records. About twenty-five Hindi or Sanskrit inscriptions, mostly of Udayesvar temple at Udaypur, are badly written, damaged and thus rendered illegible. They all belong to the 16th and 17th centuries. Two inscriptions record the construction of temples and another two of a well, a garden and a step-well (baodi).

All the Persian and Arabic inscriptions record in them the construction of mosques or are put up as epitaphs on tombs and refer to the reign of Sikandar Suri, son of Sher Shah Suri, Shah Jahan of Delhi and Mahmud Shah of Malwa. Another inscription on a baodi near Dongar, dated in Vikrama Samvat 1806 = 1749 A. D., mentions Ahmad Shah of Delhi.

One English inscription, dated 1780 A. D., is an epitaph on a tomb sacred to M. P. Lambart who met his death on June 24th and was interred there.

Two latest inscriptions at Udaygiri, dated in V. S. 1875 and 1878 (1818 and 1821 A. C.), are of little importance; the latter is engraved on a Dhupaghadi, in a circular round line along the dial.

A complete list of inscriptions with full details is given in Appendix D.

IX. Numismatics.

Twenty-one gold, 372 silver, 14 billon and 422 copper or 829 coins in all were examined during the year under report, and consist of some 43 different varieties ranging in period from 700 to 1800 A. D. (*vide* Appendix E).

Of these 20 gold, 3 silver and 26 copper coins were offered for sale by private dealers. 1 gold, 5 silver, 14 billon and 14 copper coins were received as present from the C. P. and U. P. Governments. The remaining 364 silver and 383 copper coins were received as treasure-trove finds from within the State and belong to the village Parsota (District Tonwar-ghar), Udaypur (District Bhilsa), Largakhedi of Maksudangarh Jagir in District Esagarh.

Out of the total number of coins examined 4 gold, 70 silver, 14 billon and 30 copper or 118 coins in all were selected and added to the State Archæological Museum. The remaining coins were either returned to the dealers or disposed of finally according to the current procedure. Only in one instance of treasure-trove finds from the State 20 coins were given to an informer as decided by the court concerned.

The only coin of importance acquired is that of Siladitya Yasodharman of Thaneshvar Circa 7th century A. D. Among others, next in importance may be mentioned (1) Gangeya Deva of Western Chedi, (2) Chola king Raja Raja (Circa 1000 A. D.), (3) those of Vijayanagar kings (Circa 15th century A. D.), (4) Asalla Deva of Narwar (Circa 15th century). Among the Mohammadan coins may be mentioned those of the early Sultans of Delhi not commonly met, belong to Nasir-ud-din Mohammad (Circa 1246-1265), Ala-ud-din Mahmud II Khilji (1295-1315), Qutab-Din Mubarak I (1316-1320), Gias-ud-din Tuglaq (1320-1324), Mahmud-ibn-Tuglaq (1324-1351), Sikandar Lodi (1488-1517), and Ala-ud-din Mohammad Shah II. Moghal coins are generally met with in the State finds and represent different kings and Lahore, Ahmadabad, Akbarnagar, Agra, Patna, Allahabad, Surat, Cambay, Bareilly, Kota, Murshidabad, Konch, Gwalior, Sheopor and Bhopal mint-towns. Most of these bear the regnal and A. H. years.

X. Museum.

Archæological Museum is gradually gaining in popularity and importance, a fact chiefly evidenced by the large number of visitors who pay visit to the Museum and leave their remarks on our visit-book. The signatures thus made thereon this year exceed nine hundred. Two hundred of them are from the pen of Europeans either residing in India or in different foreign countries such as U. S. A., England, France, Germany, Australia, etc. Suffice it to say that hardly any visitor to Gwalior leaves this place without seeing the Gwalior Fort and the Gujari Mahal where our Archæological Museum is located.

The actual number of visitors is far greater than that given above because some of them either do not like to sign or are illiterate and others visit headed by parties from divers institutions of arts, academy and sports, etc., whose principal or secretary only record their names. The following are some of the prominent personages who visited the Museum in the year under report :—

Mr. C. Balkrishna Rao, Executive Engineer and Director, Government Museum of Public Gardens, Trivendrum, C. M. Tembe, F. L. S., F. R. H. S., Director of Gwalior Gardens, Professor H. Hiras, Dr. D. R. Bhandarkar, Miss Stella Kramrisch, both of Calcutta University, Hon. G. Pradhan, Finance Member, Bombay Government, H. E. Lord Irwin, Viceroy and Governor-General of India, Mr. H. K. Gurtu and other delegates of the C. P. and Rajputana Federation, G. N. Mojumdar, M. L. C., Poona, Lt.-Col. C. H. Pratrish, Resident at Gwalior, Mr. J. C. Reid, Manager, *Times of India*, and the Raja of Kalakankar.

Two stone inscriptions, 12 stone sculptures and carved pieces, 118 coins of gold, silver and copper and billon and 50 miniature paintings or 192 antiquities in all were added to the Museum, during the year under report as set forth in Appendix F. Besides some fragments of the inscriptions of 10th-11th century and a few heads recovered from the debris, at Udaypur, during the conservation operations of Udayesvar temple were also brought to the Museum and will be exhibited space permitting.

To accommodate newly acquired interesting sculptures space had to be recovered in the already full room by displacing some of the less interesting of the antiquities and locating them in a lumber-room occupied only this year for this purpose and some minor alterations and additions were carried out to Building and furniture for the purpose of proper exhibition of antiquities.

XI. Miscellaneous.

(1) *Distinguished Visitors to Monuments.*—Excepting the Archæological Museum and other monuments at Gwalior, some of the important groups of Archæological Monuments, *viz.*, that of Surwaya near Shivpuri, summer capital of the State, the Bagh caves, District Amjhera, the monuments near Bhilsa and Chanderi are gaining steadily in popularity and attracting visitors from all parts. Their Excellencies Lord and Lady Irwin, Viceroy and Governor-General of India, visited in addition to the Archæological Museum, most of the monuments on the fort and the tomb of Muhammad Ghaus and Tansen at Gwalior. His Excellency the Commander-in-Chief paid a visit to the fort and some of the important monuments at Chanderi.

Besides, the signatures recorded in the visit-books kept at Surwaya, Chanderi, Bhilsa and Bagh show that the monuments were visited by numerous people.

(2) *Visit to Monuments outside the State.*—During the touring season of the year under report I visited two places outside the limits of Gwalior State, (a) Badwani and (b) Raverkhedi. Both visits were paid in response to invitations from institutions in charge of monuments at these places for consultation on technical matters and with the sanction of the Home Member Sahib.

(a) *Visit to Badwani.*—The Digambara Jaina Sri Chulagiri (Bawangaja) Sidhakshetra-prabhandha-karini Committee at Badwani, Badwani State (Central India), solicited my advice with regard to the work of restoring colossal rock-cut image of a Jaina Tirthamkara in a hill some five miles from the town. The figure, one of the biggest extent, is popularly known as Bawangaja and though very much dilapidated is still a living object of worship attracting numerous pilgrims every year. The work of repairs and additions which had been executed before my visit had gone far enough to alter the original spirit and thus to detract from the Archæological value of the monument. The committee wanted advice especially with regard to the repairs to the decayed portions of the idol proper. I suggested that it would perhaps be advisable to chisel away the decayed

surface of the rock till firm core is exposed. I advised the committee to let it alone and to construct quite a separate new building to suit the requirements of the Utsava on the bank of the river outside the reach of the floods.

(b) *Raverkhedi*.—The Utsava Mandal at Indore likewise invited me to visit the Chhatri of the Peshwa Baji Rao I, the ruins of the Peshwa's house and other monuments on the bank of the river Narbada at Raverkhedi in Khandwa District. I visited the site and the monuments in the company of Mr. D. A. Dani, a representative of the Mandal. I generally approved of the measures which the Mandal had already drawn up for the preservation of the monuments. But I did not like the iron rails which have been recently planted in the flat terrace-roof stretching a cloth-mandapa during the annual festival, for they have decidedly disfigured the archaic appearance of the monument. Nor did I approve of the white and colour wash which has been promiscuously applied even on the cut-stone work. Further I drew attention to the prevention of the washing away of the foundation of the Chhatri and Dharamshala on the south where it was being undermined by a ravine and on the north where it was being damaged by the current of the river in the monsoon floods.

Further I disagreed with the Mandal's proposal to construct a sort of *sabhamundapa* in front of the small cremation platform of the Peshwa which already exists in the bed of the river. Apart from the stability point of view of a new structure being erected in the midstream which is a point of consideration purely for engineering experts, I objected to the proposal from the view point of the least possible change in or addition to the original monument which is a recognised principle in archæological consideration. As the original cremation platform is quite safe and strong it needs no further measure for preservation.

(3) *Collection of carved stones at Bhilsa Dak Bungalow*.—A proposal of collecting carved stones from the debris of stray ruins of monuments which it was not possible to preserve on the original site, either owing to the very advanced condition of ruins or other difficulties and of using the same in modern State buildings as they have been done in the Commanding Officer's Bungalow at Goona, had been under consideration for some years past. Personally I was not much in favour of the proposal. After some arguments for and against it was resolved to drop the idea of using the old stones in new State buildings as it was undesirable from the economic, artistic and archæological standpoints and to content ourselves only with collecting interesting carvings scattered in stray ruins in the jungles and out of the way places and preserving and exhibiting them in the nearest important Dak Bungalow. Of course, carvings of the first rate importance which were worth being sent to the Archæological Museum at Gwalior, were not effected by this resolution.

It was decided that a beginning of carrying out the resolution should be made at Bhilsa Dak Bungalow and that for the present the Archæological Department should do the work out of the existing ordinary funds and the proposal of having special funds for the purpose may be considered if necessary in light of experience.

Accordingly a few sculptures and carved stones from the ruins of Besnagar, Putlighat, and Udaypur have been collected and exhibited at a cost of nearly Rs. 200 in a wooden enclosure in the garden of the Dak Bungalow at Bhilsa.

XII. Publications.

The Department published two books during the year under report. One is an illustrated Guide to Chanderi, one of the many places in Gwalior State which has made a mark in the history. The book besides giving a history of the place and describing its monuments contains information of general interest and dates for closer study of monuments.

The other book is only a short brochure for the guidance of the visitors at large for sight-seeing at Gwalior. The book besides giving a list of principal sights and short notes, contains a short sketch of the history of the ruling house of Scindias. It was brought out in haste at the request of the reception committee of the St. John Association expressly for their use. A fuller and more systematical Guide to Gwalior is yet under contemplation.

XIII. Photographs and Drawings.

One hundred ninety-two photographs were taken during the year of report. Besides, over 400 prints from the record negatives were made for the annual reports Samvat (1983-84), the Surwaya Guide, Annual Album and for supplying the various bodies for publications. Of this number the following are alone the recipients of 250 prints. (1) India Society, London, (2) Indian States Journal, Bombay, (3) D. B. Taraporewala and Sons, Bombay, (4) The Indian State Railway Magazine, (5) Dr. A. K. Coomarswamy of Boston, (6) Dr. Luders, (7) Dr. Norman Brown, (8) Mr. Richter, (9) Capt. A. R. Solly, Poona, (10) Lady Kramrich.

Twenty-two drawings both in ink and pencils were prepared, besides good many tracings made for and sent to the parties concerned for reference in connection with the Department's requisitions. For a detailed analysis see Appendices G and H.

XIV. Office Library.

One hundred fifty-four books and periodicals on History, Art, Architecture and allied subjects were added to the Office Library during the year under report. Of these 106 were purchased and the rest were received as presents from the Government of India, Provincial Governments and the Governments of Indian States and other private bodies to whom our thanks are due. The list of books added to our library is set forth in Appendix I.

XV. Income and Expenditure.

Statement of income and expenditure of the Department under different heads of the budget during the year under report are set forth in Appendices J and K from which it will be seen that the annual expenditure

was Rs. 39,488-10-6 including parts of the last year's special grants over and above the budget grant.

The income from different sources is Rs. 351-8.3 only.

XVI. Concluding Remarks.

In conclusion I am deeply grateful to Shrimant Khase Sahib Pawar, the Home Member, for the unfailing courtesy and valuable advice with which he continued to favour me in discharging the duties of the Department.

M. B. GARDE,
Superintendent Archæology,
Gwalior State

PART II.

APPENDIX A.

**Tour Diary of the Superintendent of Archaeology, Gwalior State,
for the Year 1928-29, Samvat 1985.**

Date, month and year.	Movements and Halts.	REMARKS.
23rd August 1928 ...	Gwalior to Shivpuri.	
24th ,, ...	Halt at Shivpuri.	
25th ,, ...	Shivpuri to Surwaya and back.	
26th ,, ...	Shivpuri to Gwalior.	
22nd November 1928.	Gwalior to Antri and back.	
29th ,, ...	Gwalior to Bareth.	
30th ,, ...	Bareth to Udaypur.	
1st December 1928.	Udaypur to Bhilsa <i>via</i> Bareth.	
2nd ,, ...	Bhilsa to Besnagar and back.	
3rd ,, ...	Bhilsa to Udaygiri and back.	
4th ,, ...	Bhilsa to Mhow.	
5th ,, ...	Mhow to Bagh.	
6th- 8th ,, ...	Halt at Bagh.	
9th 10th ,, ..	Bagh to Mhow.	
10th-11th ,, ...	Mhow to Badwani and back.	
12th-13th ,, ...	Mhow to Mungaoli <i>via</i> Bina.	
13th ,, ...	Mungaoli to Chanderi.	
14th ,, ..	Halt at Chanderi.	
15th ,, ..	Chanderi to Mungaoli.	
16th ,, ...	Mungaoli to Gwalior.	
11th January 1929 . .	Gwalior to Bareth.	
12th ,, ..	Bareth to Udaypur.	
13th ,, ...	Halt at Udaypur.	
14th ,, ...	Udaypur to Gwalior <i>via</i> Bareth.	
6th February 1929.	Gwalior to Udaypur.	

APPENDIX A.—(contd.)

Date, month and year.	Movements and Halts.	REMARKS.
7th-10th Feb. 1929.	Halt at Udaypur.	
11th " ...	Udaypur to Bhilsa <i>via</i> Bareth.	
12th " ...	Bhilsa to Khamb Baba and Udaygiri and back.	
13th-14th " ...	Bhilsa to Gwalior.	
14th March 1929 ...	Gwalior to Bareth.	
15th " ...	Bareth to Udaypur.	
16th-19th " ...	Halt at Udaypur.	
20th " ...	Udaypur to Bhilsa <i>via</i> Bareth.	
20th " ...	Bhilsa to Udaygiri.	
21st " ...	Halt at Udaygiri.	
22nd " ...	Udaygiri to Bhilsa.	
23rd " ...	Bhilsa to Gwalior.	
15th-16th April 1929.	Gwalior to Mhow.	
17th " ...	Mhow to Bagh.	
18th " ...	Halt at Bagh.	
19th " ...	Bagh Caves to Bagh Bungalow.	
20th " ...	Bagh to Mhow.	
21st " ...	Mhow to Ujjain.	
22nd " ...	Halt at Ujjain.	
23rd " ...	Ujjain to Mandasaur.	
24th " ...	Mandasaur to Sondni.	
24th " ...	Sondni to Mandasaur.	
25th-26th " ...	Mandasaur to Gwalior.	
28th May 1929 ...	Gwalior to Gohad.	
29th " ...	Halt at Gohad.	
30th " ...	Gohad to Pipadi, and afterwards to Gwalior.	
2nd-3rd June 1929.	Gwalior to Udaypur <i>via</i> Bareth.	
4th-5th " ...	Halt at Udaypur.	

APPENDIX A.—(concl.)

Date, month and year.	Movements and Halts.	REMARKS.
6th June 1929	... Udaypur to Bhilsa <i>via</i> Bareth.	
" "	... Bhilsa to Udaygiri.	
7th-8th	... Halt at Udaygiri.	
9th	... Udaygiri to Bhilsa.	
" "	... Bhilsa to Mhow.	
10th	... Mhow to Bagh.	
11th	... Bagh to Bagh Caves.	
12th	... Halt at Bagh Caves.	
13th	... Bagh Caves to Mhow.	
14th	... Mhow to Raverkhedi <i>via</i> Sanawad and back.	
15th	... Mhow to Ujjain.	
15th-17th	... Ujjain to Gwalior.	Break journey at Bhilsa for the inspection of Udaygiri caves.

APPENDIX B.

Statement of Monuments conserved during the Year 1928-29, Samvat 1985.

No.	Place.	Name of Monument conserved.	AMOUNT SANCTIONED.		TOTAL.	AMOUNT SPENT.		TOTAL.	REMARKS.
			Current Year.	Last Year.		Current Year.	Last Year.		
			Rs.	a. p.	Rs.	a. p.	Rs.	a. p.	
1	Lashkar	Ordinary Budget Grant.	1,606	0 0	1,606	0 0	1,564	2 3	
2	Gwalior	Chhatri of Rani of Jhansi	260	0 0	1,346	0 0	1,317	10 3	
3	Surwaya	Md. Ghaus's Tomb	10	0 0	266	12 3	10	0 0	
4	Narwar	Fort	...	...	63	9 6	259	0 9	
5	Udaypur	Minor Monuments	601	0 0	63	9 6	62	3 0	
6	"	Udaypur Temple	92	0 0	601	0 0	588	5 6	
7	Badoh	Minor Monuments	96	0 0	92	0 0	91	8 0	
8	Gwalior Fort	Putting up N. B. near con- served monuments.	84	11 9	85	0 0	81	15 9	
9	Ragh	Special repairs to Gujri Mahal	3,000	0 0	84	11 9	84	8 0	
10	Padhavli	Bagh Caves...	...	...	393	15 0	2,989	9 9	
11	Makoda	Gadhi	11	2 0	11	2 0	393	0 0	
		Putting up N. B. near Dak Bungalow.	4,059	0 0	2,737	5 6	11	2 0	
		Total	6,310	2 6	2,251	2 6	2,209	7 9	
		Special Budget Grant.	2,828	0 0	2,828	0 0	2,789	7 3	
1	Lashkar	Chhatri of Rani of Jhansi.	1,500	0 0	1,500	0 0	1,496	3 0	
2	Udaygiri	Caves	4,000	0 0	4,000	0 0	4,013	15 9	
3	Udaypur	Udayeshwar Temple	...	...	2,737	5 6	2,321	12 8	
4	Bagh	Caves	...	...	527	14 11	527	14 11	
5	Narwar	Fort	8,328	0 0	3,265	4 5	8,299	10 0	
		Total	12,387	0 0	5,516	6 11	12,321	1 3	
		GRAND TOTAL	17,903	6 11	17,903	6 11	17,380	4 7	

APPENDIX C.

Monuments Listed during the Year 1928-29, Samvat 1985.

S. No.	District.	Locality	Name of Monument.	Class.	REMARKS.
1	Esagarh.	Mungaoli.	Jama Masjid in which some pillars both carved and plain of some old Hinóu temples have been employed.	III.	
2	"	"	Malkhan baodi (step-well), with a damaged inscription circa A. H. 900 = 1494 A. D., built during the reign of Sultans of Mandu.	II.	
3	Narwar.	Bara.	An oblong step-well built with heavy blocks in which some old sculptures and carved debris are also built.	III.	
4	"	"	An uninscribed Sati-stone near cart-track ...	"	
5	"	"	Figure probably of a female (damaged) is engraved in a lotus flower above inscription.	II.	
6	"	"	An inscribed pillar set up at the entrance of the compound of a modern temple.	III.	
7	"	"	An old sculpture in the compound of the above temple.	II.	
8	"	"	An inscribed slab lying over a stone trough near a dried up step-well.	III.	
9	"	"	A mosque on top of hill in which pillars of some old temples are built up.	"	
10	"	"	A ruined tomb of some saint, dome fallen and four walls have stone screens with geometrical tracery, in Mandu Style.	II.	
11	"	Karari Ahmadpur.	An old ruined shrine of Siva	"	
12	"	"	A loose Sati-stone with worn-out inscription lying near the memorial tibaras on the outskirts of the village.	III.	
13	"	Dongar.	A step-well with inscription dated V. S. 1741.	"	
14	"	"	A mosque near above	"	
15	"	"	A tomb with an inscribed tomb-stone ...	"	
16	"	"	A step-well on old road from Narwar to Shivpuri with inscription in V. S. 1738.	"	
17	"	Tongra.	A ruined 10th century four pillared hall to the right of cart-track from Shivpuri.	II.	

APPENDIX C.—(contd.)

S. No.	District.	Locality.	Name of Monument.	Class.	REMARKS.
18	Narwar.	Tongra.	A loose stone sculpture of Nrisimha with inscription on its back.	I.	
19-22	"	"	To the right of the cart-track from Shivpuri on old site of the village a group of four 10th century ruined Hindu temples, having small oblong shrine rooms with plain walls without <i>Sikhar</i> , but has got richly carved <i>Sabhamandapa</i> or porch in front with sloping roof of over-lapping slabs with loose-sculptures.	II.	
23	"	"	A big sculpture of Hanuman near above ...	III.	
24	"	"	A Kamal Surya carved complete in a stone-block	II.	
25-26	"	"	Two temples of the above type, a furlong further towards the village on the bank of a tank.	"	
27-28	"	"	Two uninscribed Sati-stones three furlongs to the east of the town.	III.	
29-30	"	"	Two uninscribed Sati-stones half a mile to the west of the town.	"	
31	"	"	A modern tomb of a warrior ...	"	
32	"	Bhatnawar.	A ruined site of a 10th century temple beside the road south-west of the village.	"	
33	"	"	A few old sculptures in a modern room close to above known as Mata-ka-mandir.	II.	
34	"	Kalamadh.	A ruined 10th century temple of Varaha, similar to Tongra temples in style. It has a broken sculpture of Varaha and a loose Jaina sculpture near it.	"	
35	"	"	A heap of ruins of a Siva temple near the dam of a tank Kalamadh towards Berad.	III.	
36	"	Berad,	A ruined temple probably a Jaina one on the eastern extremity of the village.	"	
37	"	"	Pieces of broken Sati memorial stones with inscriptions built up in Mata temple N. of village.	"	
38	"	Bhadera.	A group of Sati-stones some of which are inscribed.	"	
39	"	Girwani.	A ruined Hindu temple similar in style to Tongra temples, on the road opposite to the village.	II.	

APPENDIX C.—(concl'd.)

S. No.	District.	Locality.	Name of Monument.	Class.	REMARKS.
40	Narwar.	Semarkhedii.	Ruins of a 10th century temple and a sculpture of Siva and Parvati, on the road below the Sarwan Tank.	III.	
41	"	"	A sculpture of a 4—armed goddess (damaged) close to the above.	"	
42	"	Shivpuri.	A tomb in Hira Shah's Takia (a bed is carved in stone which represents tomb).	II.	
43	Bhilsa.	Udaypur.	A mosque with an inscription outside Motia-Gate.	"	
44	"	"	Another mosque with inscription inside Chatua Gate.	"	
45-48	"	"	Four mosques with inscriptions.	III.	
49	Bhind.	Gohad.	Tomb of Pierre Lambert with inscription on it to the north-west of Dak Bungalow.	II.	
50	"	"	A small tomb near above	III.	
51	"	"	A pucca well with inscriptions near the above tombs.	II.	
52-53	"	Banipura.	Two Christian tombs in the field, 3½ miles to the south of Gohad.	III.	
54	"	Gohadi.	A Christian tomb (?) ½ m. to the W. of village.	"	
55	"	"	Ruins of a 10th century temple	"	
56	"	"	A loose Sati-stone lying near cart-track to the village.	"	
57	"	Pipadi.	A ruined Siva temple in the heart of the village.	"	
58	"	"	Heaps of carved debris of sites of old shrines near a tank on the north of the village.	"	
59	"	"	A crude memorial pillar on the south of the village.	"	
60	"	"	A big sculpture of Nagi in a field	"	
61	"	"	Another sculpture of Nagi close to the above in a field.	"	

APPENDIX D.

List of Inscriptions Copied or Noticed during the Year 1928-29, Samvat 1985.

Serial No.	Locality.	Object Inscribed.	Number of Lines.	Script.	Language.	Name of King.	Date.	P u r p o r t .	REMARKS.
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
		District Amjhera.							
1	Bagh Caves	A copper plate recovered from a heap of debris adjoining cave No. 2 at Bagh.	12	Gupta.	Sanskrit.	Su. bandhu.	Only the name of the month Sravana in the date remains. The rest is destroyed.	Records the grant of village Dasitha-kapali by King Subandhu of Mahishmati Nagara to Buddhist monks for their maintenance and worship of Buddha. This copper-plate has its importance in supplying an inscriptional evidence to the age of these remarkable caves, which was hitherto wanting. On paleographical grounds and in light of allied dated copper-plate inscriptions the date of our inscription may, with some certainty be restored or referred to the end of the 5th century A. D. It is therefore evident that at least some viharas at Bagh cannot be later than that date.	
2	Bhilsa.	District Bhilsa. An image of Seshshayi from Putli Ghat now kept in the garden of Dak Bungalow, Bhilsa.	2	Nagari.	Sanskrit (corrupt).	...	...	Records the making of that image by Sri Lavadeva (?).	

APPENDIX D.-- (contd.)

List of Inscriptions Copied or Noticed during the Year 1928-29, Samvat 1985.

Serial No.	Locality.	Object Inscribed.	Number of Lines.	Script.	Language.	Name of King.	Date.	P u r p o r t .	REMARKS.
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
3	Bhilsa.	An image of Seshshayi on Putli Ghat.	2	Nagari.	Sanskrit (corrupt).	...	...	Damaged and illegible.	
4	Udaygiri	A sun dial carved in rock near the passage, cave No. 20 at Udaygiri.	1 (round line).	"	Hindi.	...	Knar sudi 4, Wednesday V. S. 1878 (1821 A. D.).	The date is written in a corner and in the curve; below are several numbers such as 10, 11, 12 etc.	
5	"	In a natural rock cavern near cave No. 20 at Udaygiri.	8	"	Sanskrit (incorrect)	...	...	Text:—देहा अभिमाने गलितं विस्रायते परमात्मनि, यत्र यत्र मनो याति तत्र तत्र समाधि य [-]; इन्द्रियाणाम द्वि (धि) ष्टा (ष्ठा) वा भूताना मखिले स्व (खु) या, भूतेषु श (स) तत तस्यै व्याप्ते (स्यै) देव्यै नमो नमः, मि	
6	"	The cave under the cave No. 20.	5	"	Hindi.	...	V. S. 1875 (1818 A. D.).	One verse (श्लोका) on a metaphysical subject is written, which reads as follows:—1 ॐ रसो आअ मयो 2, औरै शौरा कार 3, सोचत जुगजुग 4, प्रेम गिर ? संत भये मो पार १८७५ संवत्.	
7	Udaypur.	Stone slab discovered in the debris on the Udayeswar temple.	18	"	Sanskrit.	...	...	Most damaged and surface totally broken off.	Illegible.

APPENDIX D.—(contd.)

List of Inscriptions Copied or Noticed during the Year 1928-29, Samvat 1985.

Serial No.	Locality.	Object Inscribed.	Number of Lines.	Script.	Language.	Name of King.	Date.	P u r p o r t .	REMARKS.
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
8	Udaypur.	A Sati-stone of Motia Gate, east porch.	5	Nagari.	Sanskrit (corrupt).	..	Kartika sudi 1, Tuesday, V. S. 1690 (1633 A D).	Records the occurrence of Sati of Gango, daughter of Galan Raina.	
9	"	A piece of stone built into the northern entrance portion of compound wall of Udayeswar temple.	4	Naskh.	Persian.	...	..	Being only the second half of an inscription, its object is not clear. It relates to some mosques and as well refers to one Abdul Rahim.	
10	"	The back of a tatti of the compound wall near the main entrance to the Udayeswar temple premises.	1	Nagari.	Hindi (Local).	...	..	Perhaps registers some grant in the following words:—राजहर देवराज नाजुल संक्राम्ति दुबेडाव [ज्वा] ल [ला] वत प्राथा (?) ३ दातव्य.	
11	"	From a piece of inscription-stone discovered from the debris of the Udayeswar temple.	14	"	Sanskrit.	...	...	Being fragmentary its purport cannot be made out.	
12	"	From a piece of stone-inscription discovered from the debris of the Udayeswar temple.	9	"	"	...	...	Do.	

APPENDIX D.—(contd.)

List of Inscriptions Copied or Noticed during Year 1928-29, Samvat 1985

Serial No.	Locality.	Object Inscribed.	Number of Lines.	Script.	Language.	Name of King.	Date.	P u r p o r t .	REMARKS.
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
13	Udaypur.	"	6	Nagari.	Sanskrit	...	...	Being fragmentary its purport cannot be made out.	
14	"	"	8	"	"	...	...	Do	
15	"	"	4	"	"	...	...	Do.	
16	"	"	12	"	"	...	...	Do,	
17	"	The side wall on the east staircase leading to the entrance.	3	"	Hindi (Local).	...	...	An imprecatory inscription. An ass and a woman are inscribed below the text.	
18	"	A carved debris of the Udayeswar temple.	1	"	"	..	..	A fragmentary piece having the name of Dhotha Pandada?	
19	"	"	1	"	"	..	...	" Mahagana, a mason's name?	
20	"	"	1	"	"	...	...	" Pajana "	
21	"	The door of Rajamandir	5	"	"	...	Chaitra sudi 1, Monday, V. S. 1699 (1642 A. D.).	A pilgrim's record, mentions a certain Bhagoti, a resident of Avanti.	

APPENDIX D.—(contd.)

List of Inscriptions Copied or Noticed during the Year 1928-29, Samvat 1985.

Serial No.	Locality.	Object Inscribed	Number of Lines.	Script.	Language.	Name of King.	Date.	P u r p o r t .	REMARKS.
22	Udaypur.	A moulded stone in the south staircase wall.	8	Hindi.	Hindi (local).	...	V. S. 1 (62) 86 (1529 A. D.).	Mentions Sri Udayeswar (Siva). Refers itself to the reign of a King [Gopa] la deva, the remaining portion is almost illegible.	
23	"	The floor of the Udayeswar temple, east porch.	3	"	"	...	...	Unintelligible.	
24	"	A stone of a wall in the mosque outside Motia Gate, east of Udaypur town.	5	Nagari.	Hindi.	Sultan Gayas Shahi of Mandu.	Katik sudi 2, Monday, V. S. 1545 (1488 A. D.).	Language irregular. Refers itself to the reign of Gayas Sahi of Mandu and the Governorship of Sher Khan of Chanderi; mentions Malava desa and Udaypur town. Records construction of a mosque, mentions names of builders, architects and so on, which are not quite legible.	
25-26	"	Built up in southern wall of Mata's temple near Kanungo's baodi at Udaypur.	2 4	Naskh Nagari.	Arabic Hindi.	Sultan Ibrahim Lodi.	Masara vadi 13, monday, V. S. 1578 (1521 A. D.).	There is a quotation from Kuran in the above two lines in Arabic. Refers itself to the reign of Sultan Ibrahim s/o Sikandar Lodi. Mentions Udaypur town included in Chanderi desa. The remaining portion being unintelligible the object is not clear.	

APPENDIX D.—(contd.)

List of Inscriptions Copied or Noticed during the Year 1928 29, Samvat 1985.

Serial No.	Locality.	Object Inscribed.	Number of Lines.	Script.	Language.	Name of King.	Date.	P u r p o r t .	REMARKS.
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
27	Udaypur.	A Sati stone in a Chhatri near Kanungo's baodi at Udaypur.	2	"	"	...	Chaitra sudi 15, V. S. 1698 (1641 A. D.).	Records Rupamati as the name of the Sati, wife of Malukchand Kaitha (Kayastha) a resident of Udaypur.	
28	"	A mosque outside Motia Gate.	3	Naskh.	Persian.	Mahmud Shah Khilji of Mandu.	A. H. 894 (1488 A. D.).	Refers to the construction of a mosque by Malik Ajabi Ataullah Gunpasta (Agent) Udaypur during the governorship of Sher Khan, governor of Chanderi in the reign of Mahmud Shah Khilji of Mandu in A. H. 894.	
29	"	A stone in the mosque near Chanderi gate.	3	Nastaliq.	"	Shah-Jahan of Delhi.	5th Ramzan A. H. 1054 (1644 A. D.).	Refers to the construction of a mosque by an Ala Bakhsh during the reign of Shah Jahan A. H. 1054.	
30	"	A stone in the mosque near Chanderi gate.	4	Nastaliq.	Persian.	Shah Jahan of Delhi.	5th Ramzan A. H. 1054 (1644 A. D.).	Refers to the construction of a mosque by Ala Bakhsh, s/o Natholi Momen (weaver) resident of Perganah Udaypur in A. H. 1054.	
31	"	Another mosque near Chanderi Gate.	3	"	Arabic.	...	...	Quotation from Kuran only.	

List of Inscriptions Copied or Noticed during the Year 1928-29, Samvat 1985.

Serial No.	Locality.	Object Inscribed.	Number of Lines.	Script.	Language.	Name of King.	Date.	P u r p o r t .	REMARKS.
1	"	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
32	"	A mosque near Chatua Darwaza.	9	"	Persian.	Islam Shah Suri.	11th Ramzan A. H. 956 (1549 A. D.)	Records the construction of a mosque in the reign of Islam Shah Suri by Masud Khan in the governorship of Changiza Khan in A. H. 956.	
33	"	Do. District Bhind.	2	"	Arabic	...	...	Quotation from Kuran.	
34	Gohad.	Stone tablet built on the tower of a tomb to the south east of Dak Bungalow.	7	Roman	English.	...	1780 A. D.	Sacred to the memory of Pierre Lambert died on June 24, 1780 A. D. aged 52.	
35	"	A block of masonry stone built as part of the wall of a well in a field near the above tomb.	6	Nagari.	Hindi.	Rana Chhatar Singh.	Chaitra sudi 11, V. S. 1839 (1782 A. D.)	Refers to the construction of a garden and a well during the reign of Rana Chhatar Singh of Gohad.	
36	"	Near the above ...	4	Nastaliq.	Persian.	"	11th Rabi-us-sani A. H. 1195 (1780 A. D.)	Same as in the above. Also mentions 23rd regnal year probably of the King of Delhi. A cross and year 1742 and letters 1 F. P.	

APPENDIX D.—(contd.)

List of Inscriptions Copied or Noticed during the Year 1928-29, Samvat 1985.

Serial No.	Locality.	Object inscribed.	Number of Lines.	Script.	Language.	Name of King.	Date.	P u r p o r t .	REMARKS.
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
37	"	Opposite to the above ones ... District Esagarh.	4	Nagari.	Hindi	...	...	Could not be deciphered from the original stone.	
38	Mungaoli.	Malkhan Baodi ... District Narwar.	...	...	Persian.	...	...	...	Not copied.
39	Bara,	A pillar in a temple ...	9	Nagari.	Hindi.	...	Vaishakha sudi 7, V. S. 1800 1743 A. D.)	Refers to the construction of a temple of Muralimanohar by Sri Boharaji Tara Chanda of Gotra mudga p Bha-raspatra (tya).	
40	"	A pillar in a temple ...	8	"	"	...	...	A pilgrim's record, Mentions Birbal, Sitaram, Phudan Chandji Ganesh Ram and Paramasukh etc.	
41	"	A stone on the baodi ...	9	"	"	Ahmad Shah.	Jetha sudi 3, Monday, V. S. 1806 (1749 A. D.).	Records the construction of the baodi by Kunwar Padam Singh s/o Thakur Man Singh in the Jagir of Arjun Singh in the time of Raja Chhatar Singhji during the reign of Ahmad Shah	

APPENDIX D.—(contd.)

List of Inscriptions Copied or Noticed during the Year 1928-29, Samvat 1985.

Serial No.	Locality.	Object Inscribed.	Number of Lines.	Script.	Language.	Name of King.	Date.	P u r p o r t .	REMARKS.
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
42	Berad, Pohri Jagir.	A piece of stone stuck up in the Mata's temple (मठ).	4	Nagari	Hindi.	...	V. S. 1639 (1582 A. D.).	Not legible.	
43	"	A stone lying near river bank probably a part of a sati.	12	"	"	...	...	...	Not copied.
44	Bhadora, Pohri Jagir.	A Sati-stone ...	3	"	"	...	Chaitra vadi 5, V. S. 1565 (1508 A. D.).	Not intelligible.	
45	"	"	7	"	"	...	V. S. 1535 (1478 A. D.).	Illegible.	
46	"	"	6	"	"	...	V. S. 1495, Saka 1360 (1438 A. D.).	Much damaged and illegible.	
47	"	"	8	"	"	...	Vaishaka vadi 14, V. S. 1668 (1611 A. D.).	Illegible.	

APPENDIX D. — (contd.)

List of Inscriptions Copied or Noticed during the Year 1928-29, Samvat 1985.

Serial No.	Locality.	Object Inscribed.	Number of Lines.	Script.	Language.	Name of King.	Date.	P u r p o r t .	REMARKS.
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
48	Dongar.	Grave stone of a tomb behind the boundary of the Zamin-dar's house of that village.	12	Nasta-liq (crude).	Persian.	...	...	Quotation from Kuran.	
49	"	A baodi behind the Zamindar's house of the village.	7 2	Nasta-liq (crude). Nagari.	Persian. Hindi.	Aurang-zeb.	Vaishakha vadi 9, Tuesday, V. S. 1747 (1690 A. D.).	Refers to the construction of a mosque and a well under the guidance of Nawab Hatam Khan during the reign of Aurangzeb. Date in Persian inscription is illegible.	
50	About a mile North of Dongar, Ranod ...	A baodi on the old Narwar Road.	12	Nagari.	Hindi.	Aurang-zeb.	Ashada sudi 3, V. S. 1738 (1681 A. D.).	It is badly written and hence not quite legible, probably records the construction of the well.	
51	"	The carved stone railing of Ghajharia Mosque.	13	Naskh.	Arabic.	...	A. H. 1040 (1630 A. D.).	Records the death of Abul Fazl in A. H. 1040. This is incomplete.	
52	"	The four sides of the lamp post of grave stone.	6	"	"	...	...	Quotation from Kuran and name of Abul Fazl, son of Sharf-ud-din.	
53	Shivpuri.	A pillar of twelve pillared tomb.	7	Nasta-liq.	Persian.	...	A. H. [9?] 66 (1558 A. D.).	Records the death of Syed Mohamad Panah, s/o Kamzan Ali Khadim (care-taker) Dargah of Muinul Chisti in the month of Shaban in A. H. [9?] 66.	Not copied, written in blank or plastered surface above the capital of a pillar.
54	"	"	6	"	"	...	...	Not legible.	

APPENDIX D.—(concl'd.)

List of Inscriptions Copied or Noticed during the Year 1928-29, Samvat 1985.

Serial No.	Locality.	Object Inscribed.	Number of Lines.	Script.	Language.	Name of King.	Date.	Purpose.	REMARKS.
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	9	9	10
55	" (Old)	A grave stone lying loose near the twelve pillared tomb along main road.	2	Nasta- liq.	Persian.	..	A. H. 998 (1589 A. D.).	Shah Abdulla and zed (descendants) of Khwaja Chisti.	Only names are given.
56	"	Jamah Masjid ...	3	"	"	Moha. mud Shah Khilji of Mandu.	A. H. 845 (1441 A. D.).	Refers to the construction of the mosque by Muhamad Shirqa and Ahmed Sher Shah during the reign of Mohamud Khilji of Malwa in A. H. 845.	
57	"	Upper and middle portions of the inscriptions on the pillars near the temple in a Bazar.	7	Naskh	"	...	7th Zikad A. H. 1040 (1630 A. D.).	It is an edict issued by Raja Sri Ram Das and warns the Jagirdaran of Perganah Shivpuri, Sarkar Nurwar, Suba Malwa.	Shivpuri is written here and not Sipri
58	"	Lower inscription on the inscribed pillar near the temple in a Bazar.	18	Nagari, Hindi.	Hindi.	...	...	Text begins thus:— इकामु फरमसु श्री पति साही etc., Purport is not clear and it is not dated, Some name of Ram Das is written on it.	
59	"	A crude stone post in Loharapara, old Shivpuri.	12	"	"	...	Vaishakha sudi 3, V. S. 1684 (1627 A. D.).	Badly written and is therefore illegible.	
60	Tongra.	The back of an image of Nrisimha.	16	Old Nagari.	Sanskrit.	...	Asbadha sudi 5 V. S. 1082 (1025 A. D.).	Records the construction of a temple of Hari (Vishnu) by name, illegible.	Now in the Archaeological Museum

APPENDIX E.

List of Coins examined during the Year 1928-29, Samvat 1985.

S.No.	Name of King.	Mint.	Metal.	Specimen.	REMARKS.
1	Siladitya of Thanesvar ...	...	Silver.	1	
2	Gangeya-Deva of Western Chedi. ...	...	Gold.	1	
3	Chola coins ...	...	Copper.	4	
4	Pandyan ...	...	"	3	
5	Chalukyan ...	...	Gold.	1	
6	Vijayanagar ...	...	"	5	
7	Do. ...	...	Copper.	7	
8	Andhra ...	...	"	1	
9	Asalla-Deva of Narwar ...	...	"	4	
10	Yadava ...	...	"	1	
11	Ceylon ...	...	Gold.	1	
12	Do ...	...	Copper.	3	
13	Nasir-ud-din Mahmud of Delhi. ...	...	Silver.	1	
14	Ala-ud-din Mahammad II ..	...	Billon.	4	
15	Kutb-ud-din Mubarik I ..	...	"	3	
16	Muhammad-ibn-tuglaq ..	...	"	2	
17	Ghias-ud-din ..	...	"	5	
18	Sikandar Lodi ...	...	Copper.	10	
19	Ghias-ud-din Khilji of Malwa ...	...	Gold.	1	
20	Akbar the great Mughal ...	Different Mints.	Silver.	10	
21	Jahangir of Delhi. ...	...	"	9	
22	Shahjahan ..	...	"	36	
23	Aurangzeb ..	...	"	33	
24	Farrukhsiyar ..	...	"	17	
25	Rafi-ud-darjat ..	...	"	1	
26	Muhammad Shah ..	...	"	5	

APPENDIX E.—(concl.)

S.No.	Name of King.	Mint.	Metal.	Specimen.	REMARKS.
27	Shah Alam II ...	...	Silver,	174	
	Indian States.				
28	Orchha ...	...	Copper.	4	
29	Conch ...	...	„	2	
30	Bhopal ...	...	„	2	
31	Gwalior ...	Sheopur	„	5	
32	Mysore ...	...	Gold.	4	
33	Do. ...	...	Copper.	1	
34	Travancore ...	...	Gold.	1	
35	Do. ...	...	Silver.	1	
36	Madura Nayak ...	...	Copper.	1	
37	East India Company	...	Silver,	1	
38	Mughal Fanam ...	...	Gold,	1	
39	Viraroya ...	...	„	2	
40	Ganga Fanam ...	...	„	1	
41	Vema Reddi ...	...	Copper.	1	
42	Venetion Sequin ...	...	Gold.	2	
43	Anonymus spherule	...	„	1	
44	Indo French ...	...	Copper.	2	
45	Punch marked modern	...	Silver.	1	
46	Do. „	...	Copper.	4	
47	Unidentified ...	...	Silver,	11	
48	Do. ...	...	Copper.	4	
49	Damaged or mutilated	...	Silver.	28	
50	Do. ...	...	Copper.	355	
	Total	...	...	829	

APPENDIX F.

**List of Antiquities added to the Archaeological Museum during the
Year 1928-29, Samvat 1985.**

Serial No.	Find-spot.	Description.	Dimensions.
Inscriptions.			
1	Bagh caves.	A copper plate inscription of Maharaja Subandhu.	10½" × 6½"
2	Tongra ...	A stone inscription in Sanskrit dated V. S. 1082.	2' × 11"
3	Chanderi.	A stone inscription in Persian ...	1'10" × 1'2"
4	Udaypur ...	A piece of stone inscription in Sanskrit.	1' × 1'7"
5	"	" " ...	1' × 9"
6	"	" " ...	1' × 9½"
7	"	" " ...	1' × 7"
8	"	" " ...	1' × 7"
9	"	" " ...	1' × 10"
Stone sculptures.			
10	Pali ...	Ardhanarisvara ...	2'9" × 1'8"
11	Bagh ...	Brahma ...	3' × 1'8"
12	Udaypur ...	Ganesa with consort ...	2' × 1'4"
13	"	Medallion with eight-armed Siva inset.	3' × 3½'
14	"	A woman ...	1'10" × 6"
15	"	A head (large) ...	2' × 9"
16	"	Face of griffin (Kirtimukha) ...	2' × 1'4"
17	"	A row of musicians ...	2'5" × 1'
18	Tongra ...	Nrisimha on the back of the inscription No. 2 above.	3'10" × 1'10"
19	Lashkar ...	Torso of Buddha (red stone) ...	2'3" × 1'
20	Udaypur ...	An architectural piece ...	3'10" × 2'1"
21	"	A head (small) ...	1' × 7" × 5"
22	"	" ...	1' × 9½" × 7"

APPENDIX F.—(contd.)

Serial No.	Find-spot.	Description.	Dimensions.
23	Udaypur.	A head (small)	1' × 9" × 7"
24	"	"	1' × 4" × 4"
Old paintings.			
25-47	Purchased.	A booklet containing pictures of 23 Jaina Tirthamkaras.	6 × 4"
48	"	A youthful pair in a humorous mood.	11" × 8½"
49	"	A female squeezing out water from her hair.	8½" × 6"
50	"	Krishna putting a ring in Radha's nose	9½" × 7"
51	"	A Muhammadan Lady looking in astonishment at a stag.	,
52	"	A female, standing, holding a flower pot.	11" × 8"
53	"	Radha and Krishna dancing ...	4½" × 5¾"
54	"	Bust of a male	11" × 8"
55	"	Siva and Parvati riding a bull and a lion respectively.	10" × 8"
56	"	A female standing facing to the right.	11" × 8"
57	"	Radha and Krishna standing facing each other.	9½" × 7"
58	"	Two females in front and one man seated above waiting to receive his beloved.	"
59	"	" " " ...	"
60	"	A Rajput warrior standing, holding a cockatoo in his right hand.	10" × 7½"
61	"	Four females facing a figure seated on a dais and enveloped all over.	9½" × 7"
62	"	Radha standing before Krishna seated on a throne and a gardener holding out a flower-pot to him.	7½" × 9½"
63	"	One young female in company of an old matron.	9½" × 7"
64	"	A female on horse back (presumably Rani Jhansi).	12" × 10"

APPENDIX F.—(contd.)

Serial No.	Find-spot.	Description.	Dimensions
65	Purchased.	Mahadji Scindia	19½" × 8"
66	"	Jiwaji Rao Scindia	12" × 9¾"
67	"		8½" × 6½"
68	"	A female dressed with tripundra on her forehead.	10½" × 7½"
69	"	Radha and Krishna in embrace ...	10" × 7¾"
70	"	Mother with a child in her lap ...	10½" × 7½"
71	"	A lady sitting along an ottoman and another playing on a tabor.	8½" × 5¾"
72	"	A Brahmana worshipping a four-armed goddess and a man wearing a Dakshini (Gwalior fashion) turban looking on.	18" × 13½"
73	"	A painting on glass, probably Queen of Jhansi on horse-back in male garb.	10" × 8"
74	"	Twelve-armed goddess riding a lion and killing a demon.	16" × 12"
75	"	Baji Rao Peshwa (?) on horse-back ...	14" × 16"
	Metal.	Coins.	Remarks.
76	Gold ...	Deva Raya II of Vijayanagar ...	Exchange.
77	"	Rama Raya	"
78	Copper ...	Sri Bhupati Raya	"
79	"	Pratap Krishna Raya	"
80	"	Sri Nilkhantha Raya	"
81	"	Samara Kolahala	"
82	"	Siluva Tirumal Raya of Vijayanagar.	"
83	"	Raja Raja of Chola	"
84	"	Sahasamalla of Ceylon ...	"
85	"	Parakramabahu of Ceylon	"
86	Gold ...	Gangeya Deva of Western Chedi ...	Presented,

APPENDIX F.—(concl.)

Serial No.	Metal.	Coins.	REMARKS.
87	Silver ...	Siladitya of Thanesar ...	Presented.
88-91	Copper ..	Asalla Deva of Narwar ...	"
92	Silver ...	Nasir-ud-din Mahmud of Delhi ...	"
93-102	Copper ...	Sikandar Lodhi of different years ...	"
103-104	Billon ...	Muhammad-Ibn-Tughlaq of different years.	"
105-109	"	Ghias-ud-din Tughlaq of different years.	"
110-113	"	Ala-ud-din Muhammad Shah II of different years.	"
114-116	"	Qutub-ud-din Mubarak I ...	"
117	Gold ...	Ghias-shah Khilji of Malwa ...	Purchased.
118-119	Silver ...	Akbar the great ...	Treasure-Trove coin.
120-123	"	Jahangir ...	"
124-128	"	Shahjahan ...	"
129-138	"	Aurangzeb ...	"
139-141	"	Farrukh Siyar ...	"
142	"	Rafi-ud-darjat ...	"
143-150	"	Muhammad Shah ...	Treasure Trove.
151-184	"	Shah Alam II ...	"
185-186	Copper ...	Konch ...	"
187-188	"	Gwalior ...	"
189-190	"	Punch marked ...	"
191-192	"	Bhopal ...	"

APPENDIX G.—(contd.).

S. No.	Locality.	Object and description.	Size.	REMARKS
23	Udaygiri.	Caves Nos. 4 to 17, general view showing the fair-weather road.	Full.	
24	"	Cave No. 5, general view	"	
25	"	" " Varaha	"	Dupl.
26	"	" " Goddess of earth and bust of Varaha.	"	
27	"	Cave No. 5, Goddess of earth	Full.	
28	"	" " showing Ganga and Yamuna	"	
29	"	" " " " and Varuna.	"	
30	"	" " Varuna	Half.	
31	"	" " Sesha	Full.	
32	"	" 6, Dwarapala and Vishnu	"	
33	"	" " Mahishamardini	Half.	
34	"	" 17, "	"	
35	"	" 19, general view	Full.	
36	"	" " "	Half.	
37	"	" " Doorway	Full.	
38	"	" " "	"	
39	"	" " Door shutters	Half	
40	"	" 20, Passage upto hill	"	
41	Udaypur.	Udayesvar temple, bird's eye-view	Full	
42	"	" " side view from south-east.	"	Dupl.
43	"	" " from South	"	
44	"	" " from West	"	
45	"	" " from north-west.	"	
46	"	" " " " " Half.		
47	"	" " " " East. Full.		
48	"	" " steps before putting up inscriptions.	"	
49	"	" " steps after putting inscription.	Half	

APPENDIX G.—(contd.)

S. No.	Locality.	Object and description.	Size.	REMARKS.
50	Udaypur.	Detached gateways on back of temple ...	Full.	
51	"	" " from north-east.	Half.	
52	"	" " from south-east.	"	
53-62	"	Courses of sculptures on the Udayesvar temple at south, west and north side (10 different negatives)	Full.	
63-77	"	Showing different sculptures on Udayesvar temple (15 plates).	Quarter.	
78	"	Udayesvar temple, panoramic view of south side.	Full.	
79	"	" " " of south side.	"	
80	"	" " " of south side.	"	
81	"	" " north-east side.	"	
82	"	" " " " ...	"	
83	"	Udayesvar temple, panoramic view, south-east side.	"	
84	"	" " " east side.	"	
85	"	" " " east side.	"	
86	"	" " " " ...	"	
87	"	" showing <i>shikhara</i> only ...	"	
88	"	" chief medallion in upper portion.	"	
89	"	" " lower " ...	"	
90	"	" medallion (complete) ...	"	
91	"	" " side view ...	"	
92	"	" detail of shikhara with medallion	"	
93	"	" sculptures in the medallion (Siva).	Half.	
94	"	" sculpture of Harihar and Siva-Parvati	Full.	
95	"	" showing a piece carved drain ...	Half.	
96	"	" shrine room in the interior ...	Full.	
97	"	" View of interior pillars ...	"	
98	"	" Bracket in the porch ...	"	
99	"	" Part of eastern door-frame ...	"	

APPENDIX G.—(contd.)

S. No.	Locality.	Object and description	Size.	REMARKS.
100	Udaypur.	Udayesar temple, ceiling of eastern porch ...	„	Dupl.
101	„	„ Vedi	„	„
102	„	„ Vedi (another view) ...	„	
103	„	„ Vedi pillar in the interior ...	„	
104	„	„ Vedi ceiling ...	„	
105	„	„ Vedi (another view) ...	„	
106	„	„ attendant shrine south-east ...	Half.	
107	„	„ „ „ south-west ...	„	
108	„	„ „ „ North ...	„	
109	„	„ door-frame of an attendant shrine,	Full.	
110	„	„ „ „ „	Half.	
111	„	compound-wall, old and new after conserva- tion,	„	
112	„	„ „ „ (another view).	„	
113	„	„ „ (original) ...	„	
114	„	compound entrance, before conservation ...	Full.	
115	„	„ „ after „ ...	„	
116	„	„ „ Dwarpala ...	Half.	
117	„	Udayesvar temple, a portion of original com- pound-wall, front view on the west.	Full.	
118	„	Pisnari-ka-temple, after clearance ...	Half.	
119	„	Shahjahani mosque, front view...	„	
120	„	„ view from south-east ...	„	
121	„	A hill in Udaypur, general view ...	„	
122	„	„ rock—sculptures Sapta Mata.	„	
123	„	„ „ „ (Navagrahas).	„	
124	„	„ „ „ of Siva, un- finished.	Full.	
125	„	Shahi Mahal, general view ...	„	
126	„	„ back view ...	„	

APPENDIX G.—(contd.)

S. No.	Locality.	Object and description.	Size.	REMARKS.
127-129	Udaypur.	Shahi Mahal, interior Jali work..	Half.	
130	"	Mosque of Mandu Sultans, general view	Full.	
131	"	Bara Khambi, general view	"	
District Gird.				
132	Lashkar.	Chhatri of Maharani Jhansi, general view from east.	Full.	
133	"	" " " view from south-east	"	
134	"	" only	"	
135	"	Entrance of Chhatri of Maharani Jhansi	"	
136	"	Statue of Mahadji Scindia, general view	"	
137	"	Mahadji Scindia's statue only	"	
138	"	" " " "	Half.	
139	"	Fort, Elephant Gate	Full.	
140	"	" Gwalipa Rishi's temple and Dharmasala	"	
141	"	" view of eastern ascent	"	
142	"	" " " another view.	"	
143	"	" western entrance with Jain sculpture.	"	
144	"	" view of western descent from west	"	
145	"	" general view showing Jain rock sculpture on west.	"	
146	"	" " " another view.	"	
147	"	" a group of rock-cut Jain sculptures	"	
148	"	" another group " "	"	
149	"	" still another group " "	"	
150	Gwalior.	Fort, rock cut Jain sculptures standing	Half.	
151	"	" A rock-cut Jain sculpture, a lady lying down perhaps Mahavir as a baby and his mother (?).	"	
152	"	" A rock-cut Jain sculpture seated	"	
153	"	" Mansingh palace out-houses	Full.	
154	"	" " " court yard No. 1, exterior face 1.	"	

APPENDIX G.—(contd.)

S. No.	Locality.	Object and description.	Size.	REMARKS.
155	Gwalior.	Fort, Mansing palace court yard No. 1, exterior face 2.	Full.	
156	"	" " court yard No. 1, exterior face 3.	"	
157	"	" " court yard No. 1, carving in the interior	"	
158	"	" " " " " "	"	
159	"	" " court yard No. 1, interior view.	"	
160	"	" " court yard No. 1, bracket.	"	
161	"	" " court yard No. 2, exterior face 1.	"	
162	"	" " court yard No. 2, exterior face another.	"	
163	"	" " court yard No. 2, decorative panel over a door.	"	
164	"	" " court yard No. 2, ceiling.	"	
165	"	" " court yard No. 2, another ceiling.	"	
166	"	Archæological Museum, a miniature painting showing worship.	"	
167	"	" " a miniature painting of Rani Jhansi	"	
168	"	" " of Baji Rao Peshwa.	"	
169	"	" " copper plate inscription (Bagh).	"	
170	"	" " " " " "	Half.	
171	"	" " Sculpture of Nrisimha with an inscription on its back from Tongra.	"	
172	"	" " Stone inscription on the back of above sculpture from Tongra.	Full.	
173	"	" " Torso of a Jain sculpture from Lashkar and a female figure from Udaypur.	Half.	
174	"	" " Ganesh with his consort from Udaypur.	"	
175	"	" " Ardh-Nariswar from Pally.	"	
176	"	" " Stone medallion with a figure of eight-armed Siva from Udaypur.	"	

APPENDIX G.—(concl'd.)

S. No.	Locality.	Object and description.	Size.	REMARKS.
177	Gwalior.	Archæological Museum, a carved stone back-rest from Udaypur.	Half.	
178	"	" " Head pieces of sculptures from Udaypur.	"	
179	"	" " Kirtimukhas from Udaypur.	"	
180	"	" " Sculptures of flying musician from Udaypur.	"	
181	"	" " Dragon's head (Brass)	"	
District Ujjain.				
182	Ujjain ...	Observatory, general view ...	Full.	
183	"	" Samrat Yantra ...	"	
184	"	" " " another ...	"	
185	"	" Nadivalaya Yantra ...	"	
186	"	" Digamsa Yantra...	"	
187	"	" Dakshinivritti Yantra ...	"	
188	"	A dilapidated building, Am-Khas near Maharaj Bada	Half.	
Miscellaneous.				
189	Gwalior.	At-Home in the Archæological Museum, Gwalior Fort.	Full.	
190	"	A map of Gwalior State, showing some places of archæological interest.	"	
191	Udaypur.	Copy of a Persian letters mentioning the names of the buildings of the Mughal mosque.	Half.	
192	"	" " " (another).	"	

APPENDIX H.

List of Drawings made during the Year 1928-29, Samvat 1985.

S.No.	Locality.	Object and description.	Size.	REMARKS.
District Bhilsa.				
1	Udaypur.	Udayesvar temple, block plan showing temple and its premises.		
2	"	" main shrine ...	...	
3	"	" Vedi and attendant shrine ...	...	
4	Bhilsa ...	Bijamandal mosque ...	...	
District Gird.				
5	Lashkar.	Chhatri of the Maharani Lakshmibai of Jhansi, site plan.		
6	"	" " " " plan.		
7	"	" Section and detail	...	
8-9	"	" Tracing ...	...	Issued to contractor.
District Narwar.				
10	Surwaya.	Surwaya Fort, plan showing the archæological monuments enclosed inside.		
11	"	" plan showing roof designs of Hindu monastery in the fort.		
District Ujjain.				
12	Ujjain ...	Chaubis khamba gate, tracing of plan	...	Sent to Munci:
13	"	Bina-nim-ki masjid, site plan, for purpose of land acquisition.		
14	"	" " tracing	...	Sent to H. M.
15	"	Map showing the probable path of the Yaksha from Ujjain to Dashapur (Mandasor) as described in the Meghaduta of Kalidasa (sketch).		
16	"	" Tracing.	...	
17	"	Observatory, site plan showing the proposed compound and retaining wall.		
18	"	Detail of above.		
19	"	Tracing from above ...	...	"
Miscellaneous.				
20	"	Map of Gwalior State showing some places of archæological interest illustrated in the album presented to H. E. the Viceroy and Governor-General of India.		
21	"	Map of Lashkar, Gwalior and Morar, showing the principal sights and communication for the pamphlet on sight-seeing in Gwalior.		
22	"	Tracing of the above ...	...	Sent to Press.

APPENDIX I.

**List of Books added to the Office Library of the Superintendent
of Archaeology, during the Year 1928-29, Samvat 1985.**

S. No.	Name and author of the book.	REMARKS.
Archaeology.		
1	Arch. Surv. of India, Annual Report 1924-25 by J. F. Blakiston.	Gratis.
2	Memoir No. 33, Pallava Architecture Part II, by A. H. Longhurst.	„
3	Do. 34, New Inscriptions of Darius from Hamadan by Prof. E. Herzfeld.	„
4	Annual Report of the Arch. Surv. of Ceylon for 1926-27, by A. M. Hocort.	„
5	Annual Report of the Mysore Arch. Dept. for the year 1927, by R. Shama Shastri.	„
6	Annual Report of the Virendra Research Society for 1927-28.	„
7	Arch. Surv. of India, Annual Report 1925-26 by J. F. Blakiston.	„
8	Annual Report of the Watson Museum of Antiquities, Rajkot by Hon. Secretary Watson Museum.	„
9	Arch. Surv. of India, Memoir No. 35, Excavations in Baluchistan 1925, Sampur Mount, Mastung and Sohr Dam Nal by H. Hergreaves.	„
Art and Architecture.		
10	The Art of Java, by O. C. Gangoli	Purchased.
11	Indian Architecture by O. C. Gangoli	„
12	Indian Art and letters Vol. II No. 1 for 1928 published by India Society.	„
13	Indian sculptures and Paintings by E. B. Havell	„
14	The Indian Art of Drawing, Pictures in the caves of Bagh by Fyzee Rahamin.	Gratis.
15	Indian Architecture Vols. 1, 2 and 3 by A. V. T. Iyer	Purchased.
16	Indian Art and letters Vol. II No. 2 for 1928	„
17	Die Indische Kunst, by Stella Kramrisch	Gratis.
18	Eastern Art Vol. I, No. 1 for 1928, by India Society	Purchased.
19	„ „ 3, 1929, „	„

APPENDIX I—(contd.)

S. No.	Name and author of the book.	REMARKS.
20	Souvenir of the Exhibition of Indian Painting for 1928, by the Society of the encourage of Indian Art, Bombay.	Gratis.
21	Hindi Silpa Sastra by K. V. Vaze	Purchased.
22	Silpa Sikshanache Mahatva by K. V. Vaze	„
23	Prachina Hindi Silpa Sastrasara by K. V. Vaze	„
24	Archaic Indian Terrakottas by A. K. Coomarswamy	„
25	Engineer's illustrated pocket book by A. V. T. Iyer	„
Books and Bibliography.		
26	Annual Bibliography of Indian Archæology for the year 1926, published by Kern Institute, Leyden.	Gratis.
27	Webster's New Modern Dictionary (English)	Purchased.
28	Persian into Marathi Dictionary by Prof M. T. Patwardhan.	„
29	Pali English Dictionary by R. C. Childers	„
Epigraphy		
30	South Indian Inscriptions Vol. III Part 4 by H. K. Sastri (copper plate grants from Sinnamanur Tirukkalar and Tiruchchengodu).	Gratis.
31	Epigraphia Indica Vol 19 Part 4	„
32	Supplement to the Annual Report on South Indian Epigraphy for the year ending 31st March 1927.	„
33	Epigraphia Indica Vol. 16 Part 6	„
34	Annual Report on South Indian Epigraphy for the year ending 31st March 1927, by G. Vyankobarao.	„
36-37	Epigraphia Indica Vol. 19 Parts 2, 3 and 4	„
Geography.		
38	Road Map of India	Purchased.
39	Map of Lashkar and Gwalior	„

APPENDIX I.—(contd.)

S. No.	Name and author of the book.	REMARKS.
Guides.		
40	At Ajanta by K. H. Vakil	Purchased
41	The illustrated guide to Gwalior and Shivpuri by B. F. Cavana.	„
42	A guide to Khajuraho by B. L. Dhama	Gratis.
History.		
43	Battle of Pratapgadha by Capt. G. V. Modak	Purchased.
44	An account of the last battle of Panipat edited by H. G. Rolinson.	„
45	Rulers of India (Harsha) by R. K. Mukerji	„
46	The Empire of the Mughals by J. H. Hoyland and S. N. Banerji.	„
47	Political History of Ancient India by R. Chaudhari	„
48	Cambridge History of India Vol. 3 Turks and Afgans by Sir W. Haig.	„
49	Anecdotes of Aurangzeb by J. N. Sarkar	„
50	Aitihāsikā Povade by Y. N. Kelkar	„
51	„ Prasthavana by V. K. Rajwade	„
52	Purandare daftar Part I by K. V. Purandare	„
53	Baudha Sanghacha Parichaya by Prof. Kaushambi	„
Iconography.		
54	South Indian Bronzes by O. C. Gangoli	„
55	The Buddha's Cuda, Hair, Unisha and crown by Koomarswamy.	„
56	Yakshas by Dr. Coomarswamy	„
Journals and Periodicals.		
57-68	Modern Reviews from July 1928 to June 1929	„
69-72	A quarterly journal of the Mythic Society Vol. 19 Parts 1 to 4.	„
73-84	Indian Antiquary from July 1928 to June 1929	„

APPENDIX I.—(contd.)

S. No.	Name and author of the book.	REMARKS.
85-87	Indian Historical Quarterly Vol. IV Nos. 2-4 ...	Purchased.
88	" " " V No. 1 ...	"
89-90	Rupam Nos. 33 to 36 edited by O. C. Gangoli ...	"
91-94	Quarterly Journal of the Andhra Historical Research Society Vol. I, Parts 1 to 4.	Gratis.
95	Do. Vol. II, Parts 3 and 4 ...	"
96	Do. Vol. III, Part I ...	"
97-100	Kashi Nagari Pracharini Patrika Vol. IX Parts 1 to 4 ...	Purchased.
101	Do. Vol. X, Part I... ..	"
102	Quarterly Journal of the Bihar and Orissa Research Society Vol. 14 Part II.	"
103	Sudha Vol. I Part I for October 1927 ...	"
104	Madhuri Vol. IV No. 2	"
105	Madhuri Vol. V Part II	"
106	Vishal Bharat for the month of January 1929 ...	"
107	Hindustan Review for April 1928	"
108-109	Sahavichara Vol. VII Nos. 4, 5 and 6	"
110-113	Bharat Itihas Samshodhak Mandal Vol. IX Nos. 1 to 4.	"
114-115	Tyaga Bhumi Vol. I, Nos. 1 to 12	Gratis.
116-121	" " II, Nos. 1 to 6	"
122	Index to Indian Antiquary Vol. LVII for the year 1928.	Purchased.
123	Bulletin of the Museum of Fine Arts Boston for October 1928.	Gratis.
124	Do. for April 1929	"
Literature.		
125	Shri Ramayan Samalochana of Ramayana's Upasamhara by Maharashtriya.	Purchased.
126	Mahabharat Adi Parva Fascicule No. 2 by Sukhatankar.	"
127	The brothers from the Bengali of Svarnalata (a novel by T. Gangoli—published by the India Society).	Gratis.

APPENDIX I.—(contd.)

S. No.	Name and author of the book.	REMARKS.
128	Mahabharata Adi Parva Fascicule No. 3 published by Sukhtankar.	Purchased.
Museum.		
129	The Indian Museum 1814 to 1914, published by trustees of the Indian Museum.	Purchased
Miscellaneous.		
130	Buddha and the Gospel of Buddhism by Coomarswamy	„
131	Proceedings of the Fourth Oriental Conference Vol. II, 1928.	Gratis.
132	Life of Maharani Lakshmbai of Jhansi by Chiplunkar.	Purchased.
133	Sanskrit culture in Modern India by Har Prasad Sastri	Gratis.
134	Proceedings of the Fifth Oriental Conference 1929 ...	„
Numismatics.		
135	Coins of the Ancients by B. V. Head	„
136	History and Coinage of Malwa by D. Whiteking ...	„
137	Coins of the Bahamani Dynasty by Codrington ...	„
138	Coins of the Gujarat Saltanat by Tailor	„
139	Numismata Orientalia, coins of Southern Indian by Sir W. Elliot.	„
140	Catalogue of Indian Coins (Greek and Scythic Kings) by P. C. Gardner.	„
State Publications.		
141	Selections of Council Orders for Samvat 1982	Gratis.
142	Annual Civil List upto June 1929	Purchased.
143	Special Gwalior State issue of the Times of India 19 August 1928.	„
144	Administration of the Gwalior State for 1924-25 ...	Gratis.
145	„ „ „ 1925-26	„
146	Gwalior State Religious Endowment Act	Purchased.

APPENDIX I.—(concl'd.)

S. No.	Name and author of the book.	REMARKS.
Photography.		
147	List of Archæological photo-negatives of the Madras Presidency and Coorg.	Gratis.
148	Picturesque India, a photographic Survey of the land of antiquity, by M. Hurliman,	Purchased.
149	List of Archæological photo-negatives of the Madras Presidency.	Gratis.
150	Excavations at Sankisa by H S. Sastri	Gratis.
151	Report on the Administration of the Archæological Department of the Cochin State for the year 1926-27.	„
152	Indian Architectural Terms by Coomarswamy ...	„
153	Arch. Surv. of India, Memoir No 36 (The Dolmens of the Pulney hills) by Rev. Anglade and Rev. Newton.	„
154	Indologica Pragensia by Winternitz and Stein ...	„

APPENDIX J.

List of Expenditure incurred during the Year 1928-29, Samvat 1985.

Serial No.	Head.	AMOUNT SPENT.		Total.
		Current year.	Last year.	
	Ordinary Budget Grant.	Rs. a. p.	Rs. a. p.	Rs. a. p.
1	Salaries ...	10,915 1 9	50 0 0	10,965 1 9
2	Travelling allowances ...	2,329 14 10	...	2,329 14 10
3	Contingency ...	1,470 0 9	...	1,470 0 9
4	Books and periodicals ...	423 6 11	70 9 6	494 0 5
5	Publication ...	599 6 0	293 4 0	892 10 0
6	Museum ...	1,793 2 3	34 11 6	1,827 13 9
7	Miscellaneous ...	454 0 0	...	454 0 0
8	General saving ...	65 0 0	...	65 0 0
9	Works.—			
	(a) Salary of staff chargeable to works.	423 9 6	...	423 9 6
	(b) Compensation of lands.	144 5 2	...	144 5 2
	(c) Formation of Museum in Dak Bungalow at Bhiisa	198 0 6	...	198 0 6
	(d) Annual upkeep and maintenance of conserved monuments.	653 13 9	...	653 13 9
	(e) Exhibiting photographs in Dak Bungalows.	126 9 0	...	126 9 0
	(f) Sending frescoes to Bombay for exhibition.	35 11 0	...	35 11 0
	(g) Conservation of ancient monuments.	4,021 7 3	2,209 7 9	6,230 15 0
	Total ...	23,653 8 8	3,007 1 1	26,660 9 9
	Special Budget Grant.			
1	Conservation works ...	8,299 10 0	2,849 11 7	11,149 5 7
2	Publication (Bagh monograph).	...	1,348 13 2	1,348 13 2
3	Famine allowance to office staff.	329 14 0	...	329 14 0
	Total ...	8,629 8 0	4,198 8 9	12,828 0 9
	GRAND TOTAL ...	32,283 0 8	7,205 9 10	39,488 10 6

APPENDIX K.

Statement of Income realised during the Year 1928-29, Samvat 1985.

S. No.	Head.	Amount.	REMARKS.
		Rs a. p.	
1	By sale of departmental publications	252 6 3	
2	By sale of tender forms... ..	14 0 0	
3	" photographs	35 6 0	
4	" old paintings... ..	44 0 0	
5	Miscellaneous	5 12 0	
	Total	351 8 3	

(a) Cave Nos. 4 and 5 at Bagh : Frescoed facade, before conservation.

(b) Cave Nos. 4 and 5 at Bagh : Frescoed facade, after conservation.

(a) Cave No. 4 at Bagh: Rail frame supporting principal doorway.

(b) Cave No. 4 at Bagh: Comparison of interior pillars before and after conservation.

(a) Cave No. 2 at Bagh : Facade after conservation from N. E.

(b) Cave No. 6 at Udaygiri : Dvarapala and Vishnu on facade.

(a) Cave No. 5 at Udaygiri : Varaha.

(b) Cave No. 5 at Udaygiri : Goddess of Earth.

(a) Cave No. 5 at Udaygiri: River goddesses Ganga and Yamuna, and Varuna the sea god.

(b) Cave No. 19 at Udaygiri: Doorway.

(a) Udayeswar temple at Udaypur : Side view from South.

(b) Udayeswar temple at Udaypur : Southern basement of shrine.

(a) Udavesvar temple at Udaypur: Principal medallion (upper portion).

(b) Udavesvar temple at Udaypur: Principal medallion (lower portion).

(a) Udayesvar temple at Udaypur : Detail of *Shikhara* with medallion.

(b) Udayesvar temple at Udaypur : *Exterior*.

(a) Udayesvar temple at Udaypur : Entrance to enclosure, before conservation.

(b) Udayesvar temple at Udaypur : Entrance to enclosure, after conservation.

(a) Udayesvar temple at Udaypur : Enclosure wall after conservation.

(b) Gwalior Fort : A Jain rock-sculpture.

(a) Shahi Mahal at Udaypur: A panel of screen work in stone.

(b) Rani of Jhansi (a painting in the Arch. Museum at Gwalior).

(a) Bajirao Peshwa (a painting in the Arch. Museum at Gwalior).

(b) Ganesha with his consort from Udaypur (now in the Arch. Museum at Gwalior).

(c) Ardha-Narasimha from Pali (now in the Arch. Museum at Gwalior).

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